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PrAEctiCe

Potentials of Agroecological practices in East Africa
with a focus on Circular water-energy-nutrient systems

Deliverable Report

D9.3 Review of ethical principles and relevant legislations

Timeline of activities: M1-M10

Work Package Leader: HKA

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Abstract	This document is Deliverable 9.3 due on M9. It provides a review of ethical principles and relevant legislations (EU & AU) to be applied to PrAectiCe activities.
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NATURE OF THE DELIVERABLE		TO R*
DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)	PU
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CLASSIFIED R-UE/ EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
CLASSIFIED C-UE/ EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
CLASSIFIED S-UE/ EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	

*R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc.

DMP: Data management plan

ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues

SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The management of risk, quality and ethics for the PrAectiCe project as part of Task 9.4 includes regular update of risk and contingency plans, setup and execution of internal peer-review process for reports and deliverables and monitoring and management of ethical and gender issues (with regular updates within the interim and periodic reports). Due to the involvement of third countries (in African Union) in the project and the use of personal data for the research, ethics plays a prominent role. An overview of all EC ethics regulations relevant to the project were compiled and all partners were briefed on this during the kick-off meeting in M1. Compliance with the GDPR for handling of personal data is ensured. It is useful to note that unlike the EU, the AU does not make laws that bind its member states, but produces conventions for adoption by its members, and provides guidance for its members on best practice in developing laws and policies, as well as occasionally producing Model Laws that member states may choose to adopt or base their national laws on.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ART-AC	Assemblée des régulateurs des télécommunications de l'Afrique Centrale (Assembly of Telecom Regulators in Central Africa)
AU	African Union
AUC	African Union Commission
CRASA	Communication Regulators' Association of South Africa
EACO	East African Communication Organisation
EC	European Commission
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EC	European Union Commission
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union
KICs	Knowledge and Innovation Communities
NDPA/RAPDP	African Network of Personal Data Protection Authorities
R&I	Research and Innovation
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESF+	European Social Fund Plus
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
WATRA	West Africa Telecommunications Regulatory Assembly

1 INTRODUCTION

PrAEctiCe aims to provide a novel set of agroecology indicators for East Africa to support smallholder farmers in their agroecological transition. The project goes beyond existing indicator frameworks by putting the 'concept into action' with a decision support tool for agroecology extension workers to help them select the most appropriate combination of agroecological practices in a local context. The project objectives will be implemented through a multi-stakeholder approach in cooperation with the European Union (EU) and the African Union (AU). Due to the involvement of third countries (in the AU) in the project and the use of personal data for research, ethics plays a prominent role. During the kick-off meeting, partners were briefed on GDPR compliance for the handling of personal data and an overview of all European Commission ethics regulations relevant to the project. Thus, rounding off the project with relevant policy recommendations for the AU and the EU.

The Review of Ethical Principles and Relevant Legislations for the PrAEctiCe project contain requirements for the Task 9.4 “Management of risks, quality, ethics and gender related issues” which are as follows:

- Ethical Framework that forms the basis for the management of ethical issues in PrAEctiCe.
- The procedures implemented to ensure the compliance with the ethical standards are presented in Chapters 2-7.
- And finally, Chapter 8 contains a short conclusion.

2 ETHICAL FRAMEWORK BASED ON EUROPEAN UNION (EU) REGULATIONS

The following ethics standards and regulations will be applied in PrAECTiCe:

- **Horizon Europe Specific Programme Decision 2021/764**
- **Horizon Europe Framework Programme Regulation 2021/695 (Article 19: Ethics)**
- **Horizon Europe - Model Grant Agreement (Article 14: Ethics and Values)**
- **Horizon Europe - Model Grant Agreement (Article 15: Data Protection)**
- **Horizon Europe - Model Grant Agreement (Article 13: Confidentiality and Security)**
- **Horizon Europe - Model Grant Agreement (Article 12: Conflict of interests)**
- **Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Article 8: Protection of personal data)**
- **European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity**
- **Global code of conduct for research in resource-poor settings (TRUST Code)**
- **Code of conduct for ethical fieldwork**
- **Code of conduct for responsible fisheries (Aquaculture fisheries in United Republic of Tanzania)**

2.1. HORIZON EUROPE SPECIFIC PROGRAMME DECISION 2021/764

Article 6: Strategic Plan¹

3. The Commission shall adopt the Strategic Plan by means of an implementing act in accordance with the examination procedure referred to in Article 14(4). That Strategic Plan shall correspond to the objectives and activities described in Annex I. That implementing act shall contain the following elements, relating to the period covered:

- (a) key strategic orientations for R&I support, including a description of expected impacts, cross-cluster issues and intervention areas covered;
- (b) identification of European Partnerships according to points (a) and (b) of Article 10 (1) of Regulation (EU) 2021/695;

¹ Council Decision (EU) 2021/764 of 10 May 2021 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, and repealing Decision 2013/743/EU (Text with EEA relevance), Official Journal of the European Union, L 167 I/1 (Legislative Acts), 12 May 2021, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021D0764>.

(c) identification of missions according to Article 7 of this Decision and Article 8 and Annex VI of Regulation (EU) 2021/695;

(d) areas for international cooperation, actions to be aligned with R&I activities of other nations and regions of the world at major scale, or actions to be carried out in cooperation with organisations in third countries;

(e) specific issues, such as: the balance between research and innovation; the integration of SSH; the role of key enabling technologies and strategic value chains; gender equality, including the integration of gender dimension in the R&I content; adherence to the highest ethics and integrity standards, and priorities for dissemination and exploitation.

4. The Strategic Plan shall take into account an analysis, conducted by the Commission, covering at least the following elements:

(a) political, socio-economic and environmental drivers which are relevant for the Union and Member States' policy priorities;

(b) the contribution of R&I to the realisation of Union policy objectives, while capitalising on studies, other scientific evidence and relevant initiatives at Union and national level, including Institutionalised European Partnerships according to point (c) of Article 10(1) of Regulation (EU) 2021/695;

(c) evidence resulting from foresight activities, science and technology indicators, innovation indicators, international developments such as the implementation of the SDGs and feedback from implementation, including monitoring the implementation of specific measures with regard to widening participation and spreading excellence and participation of SMEs;

(d) priorities with the potential to be implemented in synergy with other Union programmes;

(e) a description of the various approaches for stakeholder consultation and citizen engagement as part of the work to develop work programmes;

(f) complementarity and synergies with planning of the Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 294/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council (14).

5. The strategic planning shall be complemented by a strategic coordinating process for European Partnerships, with the participation of Member States and the Commission on an equal footing. It shall function as an entry point for foresight analysis, analysis and advice on the portfolio development, possible setup, implementation, monitoring and phasing out of R&I partnerships and be guided by a comprehensive criteria framework, based on Annex III of Regulation (EU) 2021/695.

Annex I of the Decisions mentions Ethical standards on: Industrial competitiveness, Health, Security for Society, processes and production of goods, Advance computing and Big Data, Innovation, Reforming and enhancing the European Research & Innovation System such that the strategic planning aims to:

- implement Horizon Europe's programme-level objectives in an integrated manner and provide focus on impact for Horizon Europe and provide coherence between its different parts;
- promote synergies between Horizon Europe and other Union programmes, including the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+), the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF), the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and the Euratom Programme, thereby becoming a point of reference for R&I in all related programmes across the Union budget and non-funding instruments;
- help to develop and realise Union policy for the relevant areas covered and complement policy development and implementation in the Member States;
- reduce fragmentation of efforts and avoid duplication and overlaps between funding possibilities;
- provide the framework for linking the direct research actions of the JRC and other actions supported under Horizon Europe, including the use of results and data for support to policy;
- ensure a balanced and broad approach to R&I at all stages of development, which is not only limited to fostering frontier research, the development of new products, processes and services on the basis of scientific and technological knowledge and breakthroughs, but also incorporates the use of existing technologies in novel applications and continuous improvement and non-technological and social innovation;
- ensure a systemic, cross-disciplinary, cross-sectoral and cross-policy approach to R&I in order to tackle challenges, while also giving rise to new competitive businesses and industries, fostering competition, stimulating private investment and preserving the level playing field in the internal market.

2.2. HORIZON EUROPE FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME REGULATION 2021/695

Article 19: Ethics²

1. Actions carried out under the Programme shall comply with ethical principles and relevant Union, national and international law, including the Charter and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Particular attention shall be paid to the principle of proportionality, to the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination and to the need to ensure protection of the environment and high levels of human health protection.

2. Legal entities participating in an action shall provide:

(a) an ethics self-assessment identifying and detailing all the foreseeable ethics issues related to the objective, implementation and likely impact of the activities to be funded, including a confirmation of compliance with paragraph 1 and a description of how it will be ensured;

(b) a confirmation that the activities will comply with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity published by All European Academies and that no activities excluded from funding will be conducted;

(c) for activities carried out outside the Union, a confirmation that the same activities would have been allowed in a Member State; and

(d) for activities making use of human embryonic stem cells, as appropriate, details of licensing and control measures that shall be taken by the competent authorities of the Member States concerned as well as details of the ethics approvals that shall be obtained before the activities concerned start.

3. Proposals shall be systematically screened to identify actions which raise complex or serious ethics issues and submit them to an ethics assessment. The ethics assessment shall be carried out by the Commission unless it is delegated to the funding body. All actions involving the use of human embryonic stem cells or human embryos shall be subject to an ethics assessment. Ethics screenings and assessments shall be carried out with the support of ethics

² Regulations (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 april 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No. 1290/2013 and (EU) No. 1291/2013, Official Journal of the European Union, L 170/1, 12 May 2021, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32021R0695>.

experts. The Commission and the funding bodies shall ensure the transparency of the ethics procedures without prejudice to the confidentiality of the content of those procedures.

4. Legal entities participating in an action shall obtain all approvals or other mandatory documents from the relevant national, local ethics committees or other bodies, such as data protection authorities, before the start of the relevant activities. Those documents shall be kept on file and provided to the Commission or the relevant funding body upon request.

5. If appropriate, ethics checks shall be carried out by the Commission or the relevant funding body. For serious or complex ethics issues, ethics checks shall be carried out by the Commission unless the Commission delegates this task to the funding body.

Ethics checks shall be carried out with the support of ethics experts.

6. Actions which do not fulfil the ethics requirements referred to in paragraphs 1 to 4 and are therefore not ethically acceptable, shall be rejected or terminated once the ethical unacceptability has been established.

2.3. LEGAL BASIS – HORIZON EUROPE RULES FOR PARTICIPATION: MODEL GRANT AGREEMENT

Article 14: Ethics and Values³

14.1 Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles.

Specific ethics rules as set out in Annex 5 – Ethics and research integrity³.

14.2 Values

The beneficiaries must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Specific rules on values are set out in Annex 5 – Gender mainstreaming³.

³ Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Model Grant Agreement, EU Grants: HE Unit MGA – Multi & Mono, V1.1, 15 December 2021, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/agr-contr/unit-mga_he_en.pdf.

14.3 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Chapter 5, Section 1, Article 28 – Grant Reduction³).

Such breaches may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5 –Consequences of Non-Compliance.

2.4. LEGAL BASIS – HORIZON EUROPE RULES FOR PARTICIPATION: MODEL GRANT AGREEMENT

Article 15: Data Protection³

15.1 Data processing by the granting authority

Any personal data under the Agreement will be processed under the responsibility of the data controller of the granting authority in accordance with and for the purposes set out in the Portal Privacy Statement.

For grants where the granting authority is the European Commission, an EU regulatory or executive agency, joint undertaking or other EU body, the processing will be subject to Regulation 2018/172528⁴.

15.2 Data processing by the beneficiaries

The beneficiaries must process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/67929⁵).

They must ensure that personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC (OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 39).

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC ('GDPR') (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1).

- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.

The beneficiaries may grant their personnel access to personal data only if it is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the Agreement. The beneficiaries must ensure that the personnel is under a confidentiality obligation.

The beneficiaries must inform the persons whose data are transferred to the granting authority and provide them with the Portal Privacy Statement.

15.3 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Chapter 5, Section 1, Article 28³).

Such breaches may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5³.

2.5. LEGAL BASIS – HORIZON EUROPE RULES FOR PARTICIPATION: MODEL GRANT AGREEMENT

Article 13: Confidentiality and Security³

13.1 Sensitive information

The parties must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as sensitive in writing ('sensitive information') — during the implementation of the action and for at least until the time-limit set out in the Data Sheet (see Point 6 – Other³).

If a beneficiary requests, the granting authority may agree to keep such information confidential for a longer period.

Unless otherwise agreed between the parties, they may use sensitive information only to implement the Agreement.

The beneficiaries may disclose sensitive information to their personnel or other participants involved in the action only if they:

- (a) need to know it in order to implement the Agreement and
- (b) are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

The granting authority may disclose sensitive information to its staff and to other EU institutions and bodies.

It may moreover disclose sensitive information to third parties, if:

- (a) this is necessary to implement the Agreement or safeguard the EU financial interests and
- (b) the recipients of the information are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

The confidentiality obligations no longer apply if:

- (a) the disclosing party agrees to release the other party
- (b) the information becomes publicly available, without breaching any confidentiality obligation
- (c) the disclosure of the sensitive information is required by EU, international or national law.

Specific confidentiality rules are set out in Annex 5 – Sensitive information with security recommendation³.

13.2 Classified information

The parties must handle classified information in accordance with the applicable EU, international or national law on classified information (in particular, Decision 2015/44427 and its implementing rules).

Deliverables which contain classified information must be submitted according to special procedures agreed with the granting authority.

Action tasks involving classified information may be subcontracted only after explicit approval (in writing) from the granting authority.

Classified information may not be disclosed to any third party (including participants involved in the action implementation) without prior explicit written approval from the granting authority.

Specific security rules (if any) are set out in Annex 5 – EU classified information³.

13.3 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Chapter 5, Section 1, Article 28³).

Such breaches may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5 – Consequences of Non-Compliance³.

2.6. LEGAL BASIS – HORIZON EUROPE RULES FOR PARTICIPATION: MODEL GRANT AGREEMENT

Article 12: Conflict of Interests³

12.1 Conflict of interests

The beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the Agreement could be compromised for reasons involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest ('conflict of interests').

They must formally notify the granting authority without delay of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interests and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

The granting authority may verify that the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specified deadline.

12.2 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Chapter 5, Section 1, Article 28³) and the grant or the beneficiary may be terminated (see Chapter 5, Section 2, Article 32³).

Such breaches may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5 – Consequences of Non-Compliance³.

2.7. CHARTER OF FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

Article 8: Protection of personal data⁶

1. Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.
2. Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the

⁶ Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union, Official Journal of the European Communities, 2000/C 364/1, 18.12.2000, https://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf

right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified.

3. Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority.

2.8. EUROPEAN CODE OF CONDUCT FOR RESEARCH IN INTEGRITY

The beneficiaries must respect the fundamental principle of research integrity as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity⁷.

This implies compliance with the following fundamental principles:

- **reliability** in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources;
- **honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way;
- **respect** for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment;
- **accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices and refrain from the research integrity violations described in this Code.

2.9. GLOBAL CODE OF CONDUCT FOR RESEARCH IN RESEARCH-POOR SETTINGS (TRUST CODE)

Research partnerships between high-income and lower-income settings can be highly advantageous for both parties. Or they can lead to ethics dumping, the practice of exporting unethical research practices to lower-income settings. The Global Code of Conduct for

⁷ European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity of ALLEA (All European Academies), https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/european-code-of-conduct-for-research-integrity_horizon_en.pdf.

Equitable Research Partnerships⁸ (TRUST Code) in Resource-Poor Settings counters ethics dumping by:

- providing guidance across all research disciplines
- presenting clear, short statements in simple language to achieve the highest possible accessibility
- focusing on research collaborations that entail considerable imbalances of power, resources and knowledge
- using a new framework based on the values of fairness, respect, care and honesty
- offering a wide range of learning materials and affiliated information to support the Code, and
- complementing the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity through a particular focus on research in resource-poor settings.

Those applying the Code oppose double standards in research and support long-term equitable research relationships between partners in lower-income and high-income settings based on fairness, respect, care and honesty.

2.10. CODE OF CONDUCT FOR ETHICAL FIELDWORK

The Code⁹ guides researchers to improve equity in their fieldwork, prompts reflection and conversation for better practice beyond institutional ethics review processes.

1. Setting research objectives

- Positive outcomes
- Relevant and reflect local needs
- Benefit local communities

⁸ Global code of conduct for research in resource poor settings - https://www.globalcodeofconduct.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/The_TRUST_Code.pdf.

⁹ Picot, L. E. and grasham, C. F. (2022), Code of Conduct for Ethical Fieldwork, University of Oxford, <https://researchsupport.admin.ox.ac.uk/files/ethicalfieldworkcodeofconductpdf-0>.

- Short and long term effects
- Not overstate the benefits
- Local communities and research partners should be given opportunities
- Permitting procedures for research

2. Establishing ways of working

- Prohibited in a high-income country should not be conducted
- Prioritized people's dignity, safety and wellbeing
- Socially, culturally and environmentally sensitive
- Minimize their project's environmental and carbon footprints
- Engage with all relevant ethical regulations and insurance policies
- Should not accept funding that would require unethical behaviours
- Undertake pre-fieldwork training
- Consider their physical and mental health
- Prepare contingency plans
- Know emergency help protocols

3. Working with field research staff

- Expectations
- Discuss and develop the budget with research staff
- Task and responsibilities should be equally shared among the team commiserating with expertise/abilities
- Respect local staff's knowledge
- Encourage, train and enable local researchers to lead projects
- Fairly recognize staff's contributions
- Support the staff's career development
- Fair working conditions
- No undue risk to be taken by the staff

- Protect staff from potential risks
- Set realistic expectations with local people who help offer unpaid help to the projects

4. Building cross-cultural relationships

- Advance consent of the community to commence fieldwork
- Clear, open and honest communication with the local community about the purpose of the project
- Familiarisation with cultural norms and customs
- No generalization across contexts or misassumptions of local cultural norms
- No imposition of researchers' own customs or lifestyle
- Learning local language
- Respect local communities' knowledge, experience and realities
- No engagement in relationships with research participants considering the inequalities of expectations and power
- Researchers should avoid making promises or honour the ones that are made.
- No excuse (such as illiteracy or language barrier) to give full info to participants and communities

5. Using Research Findings

- Report on matters that are well understood
- Share research findings with participants and local communities in formats/languages understood by them
- Avoid perpetuating harmful stereotypes about locals
- Engage with ethics of local media capturing
- Open access of collected data irrespective of their location
- Deposit samples/specimens at local institutions wherever possible

6. Creating a lasting positive impact

- Consider lasting positive impacts to impart within researchers' capacity
- Aim to build partnerships that will last after fieldwork ends

- Support lasting opportunities for locals with jobs and training programmes
- Must not leave behind economic or employment vacuums
- Share the lessons learnt during fieldwork with other researchers

3 ETHICAL FRAMEWORK BASED ON REGULATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF TANZANIA

Aquaculture is managed under the Fisheries Policy of 1997, the Fisheries Act No. 6 of 1970 that was amended to Act No. 22 of 2003 and the Principal Fisheries Regulations, 2004. There are also other related acts and regulations. The purpose of these regulations is to protect the environment, the producers and other resource users and ensure the safety of aquaculture products. The main regulations governing aquaculture therefore include the following Fisheries Legislation, international protocols to which The United Republic of Tanzania is a signatory or a member by accreditation (e. g CCRF - Aquaculture, i.e. the aquaculture section of the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries) and all other legislation on environmental and water resources management.

The following ethics standards and regulations will be applied in PrAEctiCe:

- **Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries (Aquaculture Ethics in Tanzania)**

3.1. CODE OF CONDUCT FOR RESPONSIBLE FISHERIES (AQUACULTURE ETHICS IN TANZANIA)

The Ethics and Sustainability of Aquaculture and Capture Fisheries¹⁰

1. Fishers / aquaculture farmers ethical principle

Work and social security: satisfactory income and safe working conditions; poverty eradication; health care, educational and other capacity-building opportunities; respect for cultural diversity.

Managerial freedom and food sovereignty in fish production systems; freedom to choose alternative livelihoods; empowerment of producers, including women and ethnic minorities; recognition of distinct identities of indigenous communities and cultural rights.

Distributive and retributive Employment opportunities for fishers/farmers; participation in decision-making; equitable and secure access to and use of resources; fair treatment in entry,

¹⁰ The Fisheries Act, 2003 (No. 22 of 2003), LEX-FAOC053024, https://www.lrct.go.tz/uploads/documents/sw-1601919334-22-2003_The%20Fisheries%20Act,%202003.pdf.

use, credit, market, trade, subsidies, regulations, policies, and law; compensation for social inequities and injustices.

2. Individual fish ethical principle

Fish welfare: maintenance of health and minimal induced pain, fear, stress, and suffering.

Freedom and flexibility to develop through various life history stages and engage in feeding, anti-predator, mating, social, schooling, and other naturally evolved behaviours for species.

Ethically acceptable or humane treatment of exploited fish in sustainable fish production systems, including selective catch and limited discards, bycatch and waste in capture fisheries, and access to food and care and protection from predators in aquaculture systems; killing without suffering; intrinsic value.

3. Ecosystem ethical principle

Ecosystem integrity: conservation of aquatic habitats, food webs, and biodiversity. Preservation of adaptive capacity and resilience to anthropogenic perturbations (e.g., fisheries, pollution, etc.).

Productive stewardship to maintain sustainability, restorative mitigation and restoration of damaged ecosystems.

4. Consumers ethical principle

Food security: access to safe, nutritious, affordable, sufficient, and culturally appropriate food.

Food sovereignty: freedom to choose desired food through eco-labelled choices of responsibly harvested seafood and culturally appropriate foods, with provenance and biological information.

Distributive Equitable access to food; no trade barriers; balance low-trophic-level forage fish consumed for food and reduced to fishmeal for high-trophic-level farmed fish production

5. Other stakeholders' ethical principle

Non-consumptive uses also valued in resource decisions, such as ecological and cultural values of fish species.

Freedom to compete for share of and access to aquatic resources; participatory decision-making and collaborative Governance.

Distributive and retributive equitable share of and access to resources for food, income, livelihood, culture, and recreation; dispute resolution for resource conflicts.

6. Future generations ethical principle

Sustainable flow of aquatic resources for benefit of future generations. Freedom to choose how resources will be utilized (not prejudiced by resource degradation or depletion).

Retributive Mitigation and restoration of ecological and social harm caused by seafood systems (e.g., reduction in fossil fuel use and global warming due to fisheries).

7. Society ethical principle

Healthy economy and environment: minimal environmental and social costs or harms from fishing and aquaculture enterprises.

Freedom to information and to express concerns about the governance of resources to ensure it benefits all of society.

Distributive minimal subsidies with fees collected by management agencies distributed to social or public programs. Retributive compensation for social or ecological harms.

8. Government ethical principle

Feasible and relatively agent's facile alternative management and policy options to serve the public interest.

Freedom to act in good faith and independently, without corruption, bribery, or unequal power relations.

Social government agents uphold the public trust without being sued, corrupted, or bribed, where decision-makers are liable, transparent, accountable, and invite public participation in debates and governance.

9. Fish population ethical principle

Fish stock abundance and genetic conservation, Behavioural freedom: free access to feeding or breeding habitats (limited migration barriers), Productive and restorative precautionary management and policies for sustaining and restoring fish biomass, growth, and reproduction to preserve species, e.g., do not catch juveniles or fecund females.

Research partnerships between high-income and lower-income settings can be highly advantageous for both parties. Or they can lead to ethics dumping, the practice of exporting unethical research practices to lower-income settings. The Global Code of Conduct for Equitable Research Partnerships⁸ (TRUST Code) in Resource-Poor Settings counters ethics dumping by:

- providing guidance across all research disciplines
- presenting clear, short statements in simple language to achieve the highest possible accessibility

- focusing on research collaborations that entail considerable imbalances of power, resources and knowledge
- using a new framework based on the values of fairness, respect, care and honesty
- offering a wide range of learning materials and affiliated information to support the Code, and
- complementing the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity through a particular focus on research in resource-poor settings.

Those applying the Code oppose double standards in research and support long-term equitable research relationships between partners in lower-income and high-income settings based on fairness, respect, care and honesty.

4 ETHICAL FRAMEWORK BASED ON REGULATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UGANDA

The following ethics standards and regulations will be applied in PrAECTiCe:

- **Data protection and privacy regulations, 2021**

4.1. DATA PROTECTION AND PRIVACY REGULATIONS, 2021 (THE REPUBLIC OF UGANDA)

The general regulations for data protection and privacy stated by the Republic of Uganda are enlisted in Part X: Regulations 47-50 of the Statutory Instruments No. 21 of 2021¹¹ along with the glossary of the relevant terms, acts, regulations, directives and bills (Data Protection Laws of the World protected by the global law firm DLA Piper¹¹).

Regulation 31: Publication of Personal Data Security Practices and Procedures¹²

- (1) For the purposes of Section 20(3) of the Data Protection and Privacy Act, 2019 – ‘Data Security Measures’¹³, the Office shall publish, in the Gazette, the generally accepted information security practices and procedures and specific industry professional rules and regulations applicable to the security of personal data.
- (2) Information security practices and procedures and specific industry professional rules and regulations applicable to the security of personal data referred to in subregulation (1) include–
 - (a) administrative measures, that is to say, measures aimed at creating efficient guidelines and security standards for dealing with personal data;
 - (b) technical measures, that is to say, measures aimed at preventing overlap and restricting access to systems and personal data.

¹¹ <https://www.dlapiperdataprotection.com/index.html?t=law&c=UG>.

¹² Statutory Instrument No. 21 of 2021, Statutory Instruments Supplement No. 10 to the Uganda Gazette No. 23, Volume CXIV, 12 March 2021, Printed by UPPC, Entebbe, by Order of the Government, https://www.dataguidance.com/sites/default/files/uganda_data_protection_regulations_small.pdf.

¹³ The Data Protection and Privacy Act, 2019, The Republic of Uganda, <https://ict.go.ug/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Data-Protection-and-Privacy-Act-2019.pdf>.

- (3) All data collectors, data processors and data controllers shall comply with the generally accepted information security practices and procedures and specific industry professional rules and regulations published by the Office under this regulation.

Regulation 32: Security Measures by Data Controller¹²

- (1) For the purposes of Section 21 of the Act – Security Measures Relating to Data Processed by Data Processor¹³, a data controller shall ensure that any data processor that processes personal data for the data controller develops and implements appropriate security measures to safeguard the personal data.
- (2) A data subject or any person who believes that a data processor is processing personal data in contravention of this regulation may make a complaint to the Office.
- (3) The complaint shall be in Form 6 in Schedule 1¹².
- (4) The complaint shall be handled in accordance with the complaints procedure specified in the Act¹³ and these Regulations.

Regulation 33: Notification of Data Security Breaches¹²

- (1) The notification required under Section 23(1) of the Act – ‘Notification of Data Security Breaches’¹³, shall be made immediately after the occurrence of the data breach.
- (2) The notification of a data breach shall be in Form 7 in Schedule 1¹².
- (3) Notwithstanding subregulation (2), the notification shall include the following-
 - (a) the nature of the personal data breach;
 - (b) the personal data which is the subject of the data breach;
 - (c) the categories and approximate number of data subjects affected by the personal data breach;
 - (d) the likely consequences of the personal data breach;
 - (e) the appropriate remedial measures taken or proposed to address the personal data breach; and
 - (f) the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other point of contact.
- (4) The Office shall, immediately after receiving a notification referred to in subregulation (1), provide the concerned data collector, data processor or data controller with appropriate guidance on how to deal with the data breach.
- (5) The guidance referred to in subregulation (4) shall include-

- (a) the remedial measures that should be taken by the data collector, data processor or data controller to deal with the data breach;
- (b) the manner of notification of the data subject affected by the data breach including requiring the data collector, data processor or data controller to provide the data subject with sufficient information relating to the data breach in order to allow the data subject to take protective measures against the consequences of the data breach;
- (c) any measures to alert the general public on the nature of the data breach; and
- (d) any additional recommended remedial measures, if any.

Regulation 34: Processing or Collection Information Without Consent¹²

(1) A data collector, data processor or data controller who collects or processes personal data without the prior consent of the data subject in contravention of Section 7(1) of the Act – ‘Consent to Collect or Process Personal Data’¹³, commits an offence and is liable, on conviction to a fine not exceeding three currency points for each day that the contravention continues or to imprisonment not exceeding six months or both.

(2) Where the offence in subregulation (1) is committed by a corporation, the corporation and every officer of the corporation who knowingly and wilfully authorises the collecting or processing of personal data in contravention of Section 7(1) of the Act¹³, commits an offence and is liable, on conviction, to a fine specified in subregulation (1).

(3) A court that convicts a data collector, data processor or data controller under subregulation (1) may in addition to the fine or imprisonment direct the Office to revoke the registration of the person.

Regulation 35: Right to Access Personal Information¹²

The request by a data subject to a data controller to confirm whether the data controller holds personal information on the data subject shall be in Form 8 in Schedule 1¹².

For the purposes of Section 24(1) of the Act – ‘Right to Access Personal Information’¹³, a data subject satisfies the requirement of proof of identity, where the data subject provides any of the following:

- (a) a national identification card or aliens identification card;
- (b) a passport or any travel document; or
- (c) a drivers licence.

(3) A data controller shall inform the data subject of its decision within seven days after receipt of the request.

(4) Where a data controller refuses the request of the data subject, the data controller shall state the reasons for the refusal.

Regulation 36: Right to Prevent Processing of Personal Data¹²

(1) A data subject may, by notice in writing to a data controller or data processor, require the data controller or data processor to cease the processing or further processing of personal data where the processing or further processing is not compatible with the purpose for which the personal data was collected.

(2) A data controller or data processor shall, within fourteen days after receipt of the notice, inform the data subject in writing that the data controller or data processor has complied or intends to comply with the notice of the data subject.

(3) Where a data controller or data processor does not comply with the notice, the data controller or data processor shall state the reasons for non-compliance.

(4) Where the data controller gives reasons for non-compliance, a copy of the notice required by subregulation (2) shall be given to the Office within seven days.

(5) Where the Office does not agree with the reasons for non-compliance, the Office shall direct the data controller or data processor to comply with the notice of the data subject within seven days.

Regulation 40: Complaints Handling by Data Collectors, Data Processors and Data Controllers¹²

Every data collector, data controller and data processor shall develop and implement a complaints handling system to deal with complaints from data subjects.

Section 41: Complaints Against Breach and Noncompliance¹²

(1) Where-

(a) a data subject or any person believes that a data collector, data processor or data controller is infringing on his or her rights or is in violation of the Act¹³, the data subject or person may make a complaint to the Office; or

(b) the Director is of the opinion that a data collector, data processor or data controller is infringing or is in violation of the Act¹³, the Director may serve a notice on such data collector, data processor or data controller requiring the data collector, data processor or data controller to take such remedial action within such period as may be specified in the notice.

(2) For the purposes of subregulation (1)(a), a complaint shall be in Form 11 in Schedule 1¹².

(3) Every complaint shall be addressed to the Director.

(4) This regulation does not apply to complaints made under Regulation 39(3) – Rectification, Blocking, Erasure and Destruction of Personal Data¹².

5 ETHICAL FRAMEWORK BASED ON REGULATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF KENYA

The Office of the Data Protection Commissioner¹⁴ (ODPC) in Kenya is tasked with overseeing implementation and enforcement of all the statutes on data protection. The ODPC has issued several guidelines on data handling, processing and management based on the Data Protection Act of 2019¹⁵. The following ethics standards and regulations will be applied in PrAEctiCe:

- **Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (Article 31: Privacy)**
- **Data Protection (General) Regulations, 2021**
- **Data Protection (Registration of Data Controllers and Data Processors) Regulations, 2021**
- **Data Protection (Complaints Handling and Enforcement Procedures) Regulations, 2021**

5.1. RIGHTS AND FUNDAMENTAL FREEDOMS

Article 31: Privacy¹⁶

Every person has the right to privacy, which includes the right not to have—

- (a) their person, home or property searched;
- (b) their possessions seized;
- (c) information relating to their family or private affairs unnecessarily required or revealed; or
- (d) the privacy of their communications infringed.

¹⁴ www.odpc.go.ke

¹⁵ Kenya Gazette Supplement No. 181 (Acts No. 24), Page 901-948, Nairobi, 11 November 2019, <https://www.odpc.go.ke/download/kenya-gazette-data-protection-act-2019/?wpdmdl=3235&refresh=64fecbf6e03c31694419958>.

¹⁶ Laws of Kenya, Constitution of Kenya, 2010, Published by the National Council for Law Reporting with the Authority of the Attorney-General, www.kenyalaw.org, <https://eregulations.invest.go.ke/media/ConstitutionofKenya%202010.pdf>.

5.2. DATA PROTECTION (GENERAL) REGULATIONS, 2021

Regulation 23: Data Protection Policy¹⁷

Every person has the right to privacy, which includes the right not to have—

- (a) their person, home or property searched;
- (b) their possessions seized;
- (c) information relating to their family or private affairs unnecessarily required or revealed; or
- (d) the privacy of their communications infringed.

Regulation 25: Obligations of a Data Processor¹⁷

Every person has the right to privacy, which includes the right not to have—

- (a) their person, home or property searched;
- (b) their possessions seized;
- (c) information relating to their family or private affairs unnecessarily required or revealed; or
- (d) the privacy of their communications infringed.

Regulation 26: Requirement for Specified Processing Data to be Done in Kenya¹⁷

Every person has the right to privacy, which includes the right not to have—

- (a) their person, home or property searched;
- (b) their possessions seized;
- (c) information relating to their family or private affairs unnecessarily required or revealed; or
- (d) the privacy of their communications infringed.

¹⁷ The Data Protection (General) Regulations, 2021 Arrangement of Regulations, Special Issue Kenya Gazette Supplement No. 236, Legislative Supplement No. 106, Legal Notice No. 263, 31st December 2021, <https://www.odpc.go.ke/download/the-data-protection-general-regulations-2021-2/?wpdmml=8946&refresh=650072b257c871694528178>.

Part V – Elements to Implement Data Protection by Design or by Default (Regulations 27-36)¹⁷

27. A data collector or data processor shall in processing of personal data—
- (a) establish the data protection mechanisms set out under the Act¹⁵ and these Regulations are embedded in the processing; and
 - (b) design technical and organisational measure to safeguard and implement the data protection principles.
28. The elements for the protection of personal data by design or by default that are necessary to implement the data protection principles outlined under Section 25 of the Act¹⁵ are as set out in this Part V.
29. The elements necessary to implement the principle of lawfulness include—
- (a) appropriate legal basis or legitimate interests clearly connected to the specific purpose of processing;
 - (b) processing that is necessary for the purpose;
 - (c) the data subject being granted the highest degree of autonomy possible with respect to control over their personal data;
 - (d) a data subject knowing what they consented to and a simplified means to withdraw consent; and
 - (e) restriction of processing where the legal basis or legitimate interests ceases to apply.
30. The elements necessary to implement the principle of transparency include—
- (a) the use of clear, simple and plain language to communicate with a data subject to enable a data subject to make decisions on the processing of their personal data;
 - (b) making the information on the processing easily accessible to the data subject;
 - (c) providing the information on the processing to the data subject at the relevant time and in the appropriate form;
 - (d) the use of machine-readable language to facilitate and automate readability and clarity;
 - (e) providing a fair understanding of the expectation with regards to the processing particularly for children or other vulnerable groups; and
 - (f) providing details of the use and disclosure of the personal data of a data subject.
31. The elements necessary to implement the principle of purpose limitation include—

- (a) specifying the purpose for each processing of personal data;
 - (b) determining the legitimate purposes for the processing of personal data before designing organisational measures and safeguards;
 - (c) the purpose for the processing being the determinant for personal data collected;
 - (d) ensuring a new purpose is compatible with the original purpose for which the data was collected;
 - (e) regularly reviewing whether the processing is necessary for the purposes for which the data was collected and test the design against purpose limitation; and
 - (f) the use of technical measures, including hashing and cryptography, to limit the possibility of repurposing personal data.
32. The elements necessary to implement the principle of integrity, confidentiality and availability include—
- (a) having an operative means of managing policies and procedures for information security;
 - (b) assessing the risks against the security of personal data and putting in place measures to counter identified risks;
 - (c) processing that is robust to withstand changes, regulatory demands, incidents, and cyber-attacks;
 - (d) ensuring only authorised personnel have access to the data necessary for their processing tasks;
 - (e) securing transfers shall be secured against unauthorised access and changes;
 - (f) securing data storage from use, unauthorised access and alterations;
 - (g) keeping back-ups and logs to the extent necessary for information security;
 - (h) using audit trails and event monitoring as a routine security control;
 - (i) protecting sensitive personal data with adequate measures and, where possible, kept separate from the rest of the personal data;
 - (j) having in place routines and procedures to detect, handle, report, and learn from data breaches; and
 - (k) regularly reviewing and testing software to uncover vulnerabilities of the systems supporting the processing.

33. The elements necessary to implement the principle of data minimization include—

- (a) avoiding the processing of personal data altogether when this is possible for the relevant purpose;
- (b) limiting the amount of personal data collected to what is necessary for the purpose;
- (c) ability to demonstrate the relevance of the data to the processing in question;
- (d) pseudonymising personal data as soon as the data is no longer necessary to have directly identifiable personal data, and storing identification keys separately;
- (e) anonymizing or deleting personal data where the data is no longer necessary for the purpose;
- (f) making data flows efficient to avoid the creation of more copies or entry points for data collection than is necessary; and
- (g) the application of available and suitable technologies for data avoidance and minimization.

34. The elements necessary to implement the principle of accuracy include—

- (a) ensuring data sources are reliable in terms of data accuracy;
- (b) having personal data particulars being accurate as necessary for the specified purposes;
- (c) verification of the correctness of personal data with the data subject before and at different stages of the processing depending on the nature of the personal data, in relation to how often it may change;
- (d) erasing or rectifying inaccurate data without delay;
- (e) mitigating the effect of an accumulated error in the processing chain;
- (f) giving data subjects an overview and easy access to personal data in order to control accuracy and rectify as needed;
- (g) having personal data accurate at all stages of the processing and carrying out tests for accuracy at critical steps;
- (h) updating personal data as necessary for the purpose; and
- (i) the use of technological and organisational design features to decrease inaccuracy.

35. The elements necessary to implement the principle of storage limitation include—

- (a) having clear internal procedures for deletion and destruction;

- (b) determining what data and length of storage of personal data that is necessary for the purpose;
- (c) formulating internal retention statements of implementing them;
- (d) ensuring that it is not possible to re-identify anonymised data or recover deleted data and testing whether this is possible;
- (e) the ability to justify why the period of storage is necessary for the purpose, and disclosing the rationale behind the retention period; and
- (f) determining which personal data and length of storage is necessary for back-ups and logs.

36. The elements necessary to implement the principle of fairness include—

- (a) granting the data subjects the highest degree of autonomy with respect to control over their personal data;
- (b) enabling a data subject to communicate and exercise their rights;
- (c) elimination of any discrimination against a data subject;
- (d) guarding against the exploitation of the needs or vulnerabilities of a data subject; and
- (e) incorporating human intervention to minimize biases that automated decision-making processes may create.

Part VII – Transfer of Personal Data Outside Kenya (Regulations 39 - 48)¹⁷

39. In this Part, unless the context otherwise requires –

- (a) “data in transit” means personal data transferred through Kenya in the course of onward transportation to a country or territory outside Kenya, without the personal data being accessed or used by, or disclosed to, any entity while in Kenya, except for the purpose of such transportation;
- (b) “recipient” means an entity that receives in a country or territory outside Kenya the personal data transferred to the recipient by or on behalf of the transferring entity, but does not include an entity that receives the personal data solely as a network service provider or carrier;
- (c) “transferring entity” means an entity that transfers personal data from Kenya to a country or a territory outside Kenya but does not include an entity dealing with data in transit; and
- (d) “relevant international organisation” means an international organisation that carries out functions for any of the law enforcement purposes.

40. A data controller or data processor who is a transferring entity shall before transferring personal data out of Kenya ascertain that the transfer is based on—
- (a) appropriate data protection safeguards;
 - (b) an adequacy decision made by the Data Commissioner;
 - (c) transfer as a necessity; or
 - (d) consent of the data subject.
41. (1) A transfer of personal data to another country or a relevant international organisation is based on the existence of appropriate safeguards where—
- (a) a legal instrument containing appropriate safeguards for the protection of personal data binding the intended recipient that is essentially equivalent to the protection under the Act and these Regulations; or
 - (b) the data controller, having assessed all the circumstances surrounding transfers of that type of personal data to another country or relevant international organisation, concludes that appropriate safeguards exist to protect the data.
- (2) Where a transfer of data takes place in reliance on sub- regulation (1) —
- (a) the transfer shall be documented;
 - (b) the documentation shall be provided to the Commissioner on request; and
 - (c) the documentation shall include—
 - (i) the date and time of the transfer;
 - (ii) the name of the recipient;
 - (iii) the justification for the transfer; and
 - (iv) a description of the personal data transferred.
42. For the purpose of confirming the existence of appropriate data protection safeguards anticipated under Section 49 (1) of the Act¹⁵ and these Regulations, any country or a territory is taken to have such safeguards if that country or territory has—
- (a) ratified the African Union Convention on Cyber Security and Personal Data Protection;
 - (b) a reciprocal data protection agreement with Kenya; or
 - (c) a contractual binding corporate rules among a concerned group of undertakings or enterprises.

43. (1) The contractual binding corporate rules contemplated under Regulation 41 shall be valid if they—
- (a) are legally binding and apply to and are enforced by every member concerned of the group of undertakings, or group of enterprises engaged in a joint economic activity, including their employees;
 - (b) expressly confer enforceable rights on data subjects with regard to the processing of their personal data; and
 - (c) fulfil the requirements laid down in sub-regulation (2).
- (2) The binding corporate rules referred to in sub-regulation (1) shall specify—
- (a) the structure and contact details of the group of undertakings, or group of enterprises engaged in a joint economic activity and of each of its members;
 - (b) the data transfers or set of transfers, including the categories of personal data, the type of processing and its purposes, the type of data subjects affected and the identification of another country or countries in question;
 - (c) their legally binding nature, both internally and externally;
 - (d) the application of the general data protection principles;
 - (e) the rights of data subjects in regard to processing and the means to exercise those rights;
 - (f) the complaint procedures; and
 - (g) the mechanisms within the group of undertakings, or group of enterprises engaged in a joint economic activity for ensuring the verification of compliance with the binding corporate rules.
44. (1) A transfer of personal data to another country or a relevant international organization is based on an adequacy decision where the Data Commissioner makes a decision that—
- (a) the other country or a territory or one or more specified sectors within that other country, or
 - (b) the international organization, ensures an adequate level of protection of personal data.
- (2) The Data Commissioner may publish on its website a list of the countries, territories and specified sectors within that other country and relevant international organisation for which the Data Commissioner has made a decision that an adequate level of protection is ensured.

45. (1) Personal data may be transferred to another country or territory on the basis of necessity if such a transfer is necessary for any of the purposes outlined under section 48(c) of the Act¹⁵.
- (2) Prior to making a transfer under sub-regulation (1), a transferring entity shall ascertain that—
- (a) that the transfer is strictly necessary in a specific case outlined under section 48(c) of the Act¹⁵;
 - (b) there are no fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject concerned that override the public interest necessitating the transfer.
- (3) This section does not affect the operation of any international agreement in force between Kenya and other countries in the field of judicial co-operation in criminal matters and police co-operation.
46. (1) In accordance with section 25 (g) of the Act¹⁵, in the absence of an adequacy decision, appropriate safeguards or prerequisites for transfer as a necessity, a transfer or a set of transfers of personal data to another country shall take place only on the condition that the data subject—
- (a) has explicitly consented to the proposed transfer; and
 - (b) has been informed of the possible risks of such transfers.
- (2) Without limiting the generality of sub-regulation (1), a data controller or processor must seek consent from a data subject for the transfer of sensitive personal data, in accordance with section 49 of the Act¹⁵.
47. (1) Where personal data is transferred in accordance with this Part, the entity effecting the transfer shall make it a condition of the transfer, that the data is not to be further transferred to another country or territory without the authorisation of the transferring entity or another competent authority.
- (2) A competent authority may give an authorisation under sub-regulation (1) only where the further transfer is necessary for a law enforcement purpose.
48. A transferring entity may enter into a written agreement with the recipient of personal data, which shall contain provisions relating to—
- (a) unlimited access by the transferring entity to ascertain the existence of a robust information system of the recipient for storing the personal data; and
 - (b) the countries and territories to which the personal data may be transferred under the contract.

Part VIII – Data Protection Impact Assessment (Regulations 49 - 53)¹⁷

49. (1) For the purpose of section 31 (1) of the Act¹⁵, processing operations considered to result in high risks to the rights and freedoms of a data subject include —

- (a) automated decision making with legal or similar significant effect that includes the use of profiling or algorithmic means or use of sensitive personal data as an element to determine access to services or that results in legal or similarly significant effects;
- (b) use of personal data on a large-scale for a purpose other than that for which the data was initially collected;
- (c) processing biometric or genetic data;
- (d) where there is a change in any aspect of the processing that may result in higher risk to data subjects;
- (e) processing sensitive personal data or data relating to children or vulnerable groups;
- (f) combining, linking or cross-referencing separate datasets where the data sets are combined from different sources and where processing is carried out for different purposes;
- (g) large scale processing of personal data;
- (h) a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale;
- (i) innovative use or application of new technological or organizational solutions; or
- (j) where the processing prevents a data subject from exercising a right.

(2) A data processor or data controller shall, prior to processing data under sub-regulation (1) conduct a data protection impact assessment.

50. (1) Where a data protection impact assessment is required, a data controller or data processor may conduct the assessment through a template set out in the Third Schedule.

(2) Despite sub-regulation (1), a format of the data protection impact assessment may be varied by the Data Commissioner through guidance notes as may be issued from time to time.

51. (1) In accordance with section 31 (3) of the Act¹⁵, where a data controller or a data processor is required to consult the Data Commissioner on the data protection impact assessment prior to processing, such consultations shall be done within sixty days from the date of the receipt of the impact statement report.

(2) In making a request under sub-regulation (1), the data controller or data processor shall provide—

(a) the data protection impact assessment prepared under section 31(1) of the Act¹⁵; and

(b) where applicable, the respective responsibilities of the data controller or data processors involved in the processing.

(3) Where the Data Commissioner considers that the intended processing is likely to infringe on the Act¹⁵ or these Regulations, the Data Commissioner may issue such advice to the data controller or the data processor, in writing.

52. (1) In conducting a data protection impact assessment, a data controller or a data processor may consult the Office for advice on whether risks identified and mitigation measures suggested are viable in the outlined circumstances.

(2) In reviewing the data protection impact assessment report, the Data Commissioner may make any recommendations to be incorporated prior to commencing the processing operations.

(3) Where a data controller or data processor, upon submitting the data protection impact assessment report to the Data Commissioner, does not receive any communication within sixty days of submission, may commence processing operations and the assessment report shall be taken to have been approved.

(4) A data controller or data processor may publish on its website the data protection impact assessment Report.

53. Pursuant to section 23 of the Act¹⁵, the Data Commissioner may carry out periodic audits to monitor compliance with the Assessment Report and any recommendations that may have been provided by the Data Commissioner.

Part IX – Provisions on Exemption Under the Act (Regulation 58)¹⁷

58. A person aggrieved by a decision of a data controller or a data processor under this Regulation or non-compliance with any provision may lodge a complaint with the Data Commissioner in accordance with the Act¹⁵ and regulations on complaints handling made thereunder.

5.3. DATA PROTECTION (REGISTRATION OF DATA CONTROLLERS AND DATA PROCESSORS) REGULATIONS, 2021

3. (1) These Regulations¹⁸ provide for the procedure for registration of data controllers and data processors as provided under section 18 of the Act.

(2) These Regulations¹⁸ shall not apply to civil registration entities specified under the Data Protection (Civil Registration) Regulations, 2020.
4. (1) Subject to regulation 13 (1), every data controller and data processor shall be required to register in accordance with the provisions of the Act and these Regulations.

(2) For purposes of registration, a person shall register as a –
 - (a) data controller, where the person determines the purpose and means for processing personal data; or
 - (b) data processor, where the person processes personal data on behalf of the data controller but excludes employees of the data controller and has –
 - (i) a contractual relationship with the data controller; and
 - (ii) no decision making power on the purpose and means of processing personal data.
(3) Despite sub-regulation (2) (a), a data controller may apply for registration as both a data controller and a data processor with regards to any processing operations and shall be required to pay the requisite fees applicable for both a data controller and a data processor thereto.

(4) Despite sub-regulation (2) (b), where a data processor processes personal data other than as instructed by the data controller, the data processor shall be considered to be a data controller in respect of that processing activity, for purposes of assessing liability.
5. (1) An application for registration of a data controller or data processor shall –

¹⁸ The Data Protection (Registration of Data Controllers and Data Processors) Regulations, 2021, Legal Notice No. 265, Kenya Subsidiary Legislation, 2021, <https://www.odpc.go.ke/download/the-data-protection-registration-of-data-controllers-and-data-processors-regulations-2021-2/>

- (a) be in Form DPR1 set out in the First Schedule¹⁸; and
 - (b) be accompanied by the registration fees specified in the Second Schedule¹⁸.
- (2) An application for registration under sub-regulation (1) shall be accompanied by
- (a) a copy of the establishment documents;
 - (b) particulars of the data controllers or data processors including name and contact details;
 - (c) a description of the purpose for which personal data is processed; and
 - (d) a description of categories of personal data being processed.
6. (1) A state department or county department shall register and pay the fees on behalf of their respective entities.
- (2) The entities referred to under sub-regulation (1) shall be the public entities at national or county government which –
- (a) operates within a state department or county department;
 - (b) is wholly funded from the Consolidated Fund; and
 - (c) provides a public service.
- (3) The fees paid by the state department or county department under sub-regulation (1) shall cater for the specified entities registered under the concerned state department or county department.
- (4) Despite this regulation, a State Corporation or a County Corporation shall be required to register as a data controller or a data processor in respect of their processing activity, in the manner specified under these Regulations¹⁸.
16. (1) Subject to section 22 of the Act¹⁵, the Data Commissioner may cancel a certificate of registration or vary the conditions for registration, where –
- (a) the data controller or data processor applies for cancellation or variation;
 - (b) the Data Commissioner establishes that the data controller or data processor provided false or misleading information in relation to any registration particulars; or
 - (c) the data controller or data processor willfully or negligently, fails to comply with provisions of the Act and any Regulations made thereunder.
- (2) The Data Commissioner shall, before cancelling or varying the conditions of registration, be guided by the provisions of the Fair Administrative Actions Act, 2015.

17. An application made under these Regulations¹⁸ shall be submitted through electronic means provided for on the Office website.

18. A data controller or a data processor who –

(a) processes personal data without registering in accordance with these Regulations¹⁸;

(b) provides false or misleading information for the purpose of registration; or

(c) fails to renew a certificate of registration and continues to process personal data after the expiry of the certificate,

commits an offence and shall, upon conviction, be liable to penalty specified under section 73 of the Act¹⁵.

5.4. DATA PROTECTION (COMPLAINTS HANDLING AND ENFORCEMENT PROCEDURES) REGULATIONS, 2021

3. The object and purpose of these Regulations¹⁹ is to –

(a) facilitate a fair, impartial, just, expeditious, proportionate and affordable determination of complaints lodged with the Data Commissioner in accordance with the Act and these Regulations, without undue regard to technicalities of procedure;

(b) provide for issuance of enforcement notices as contemplated under section 58 of the Act¹⁵;

(c) provide for issuance of issuance of penalty notices as contemplated under section 62 of the Act¹⁵;

(d) provide for the procedure for hearing and determining of complaints; and

(e) provide for the resolution of complaints lodged with the Data Commissioner by means of alternative dispute resolution mechanisms as specified under section 9(1) (c) of the Act¹⁵.

Part II – Procedure for Lodging, Admission and Response to Complaints¹⁹

¹⁹ The Data Protection (Complaints Handling and Enforcement Procedures) Regulations, 2021, Legal Notice No. 264, Kenya Subsidiary Legislation, 2021, <https://www.odpc.go.ke/download/the-data-protection-complaints-handling-and-enforcement-regulations-2021/>

Regulation 4 – Lodging of a complaint (Pursuant to Section 56 of the Act¹⁵)

Regulation 5 – Register of complaints (shall be lodged free of charge with the Data Commissioner under sub-regulation (1) of regulation 5¹⁹)

Regulation 6 – Admission of complaint (advise the complainant in writing and refer to the relevant body or institution if needed)

Regulation 7 – Discontinuation of a complaint (discontinue existing complaint or reinstitute a discontinued complaint by the Data Commissioner)

Regulation 8 – Withdrawal of complaints (or re-lodge withdrawn complaint)

Regulation 9 – Joint consideration of complaints (Data Commissioner may consolidate complaints on similar issues)

Regulation 10 – Language for the proceedings shall be Kiswahili, English or Kenyan Sign Language (with interpreter by the Office for party who cannot speak, hear or understand the language of proceedings)

Regulation 11 – Notification of a complaint to the respondent (Data Commissioner notifies the respondent to respond within 21 days with relevant materials or evidence)

Regulation 12 – Joinder of parties (person who has interest in the outcome of a complaint may apply to the Office to join the complaint party or leave to be enjoined in the proceedings prior to the hearing of the complaint)

Regulation 13 – Investigations of a complaint (by the Data Commissioner guided by the Fair Administrative Action Act, 2015)

Regulation 14 – Outcome of the investigation (Data Commissioner make a determination based on the findings of the investigations)

Regulation 15 – Negotiation, mediation or conciliation (between the complainant and the Data Commissioner)

Part III – Enforcement Provisions¹⁹

Regulation 16 – Issuance of enforcement notice (by the Data Commissioner as per Section 58 of the Act¹⁵)

Regulation 17 – Service of an enforcement notice

Regulation 18 – Review of enforcement notice (requested by the Data Commissioner by the person who is served an enforcement notice)

Regulation 19 – Appeals against enforcement notice (to the High Court, subject to Sections 58 (2) (d) and 64 of the Act¹⁵)

Regulaiton 20 – Issuance of penalty notice (Under Section 62 of the Act¹⁵)

Regulaiton 21 – Enforcement of penalty notice (on the lapse of the period given by the Data Commissioner to appeal against the penalty).

6 ETHICAL FRAMEWORK BASED ON REGULATIONS IN THE AFRICAN UNION (AU)

In 2014, the AU adopted a continental convention titled The African Union Convention on Cyber Security and Personal Data Protection (also known as the “Malabo Convention”²⁰). Its purpose is to establish a “credible framework for cybersecurity in Africa through the organisation of electronic transactions, protection of personal data, promotion of cyber security, e-governance, and combating cybercrime.” This is set to come into force after Mauritania became the 15th state to submit its ratification. The Convention entered into force on 8 June 2023. A status list²¹ on the Convention showing that the AU received Mauritania’s ratification on 12 May 2023 is provided in Annex I. Currently the three target countries of this PrAECTiCe project – Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda have not yet signed up. Tanzania has developed its own data protection act, in Kiswahili²².

The AU has also produced the AU Data Policy Framework. The purpose of this document is “to provide the policy framework for African countries to maximise the benefits of a data-driven economy by creating an enabling policy environment for the private and public investments necessary to support data-driven value creation and innovation.”

The following ethics standards and regulations will be applied in PrAECTiCe:

- **AU Convention on Cyber Security and Personal Data Protection (Preamble)**²³
- **AU Data Policy Framework**²⁴
- **The Malabo Roadmap**²⁰

²⁰ The Malabo Roadmap: Approaches to promote data protection and data governance in Africa, September 2022, Prepared for the Mozilla Africa Mradi programme by ALT Advisory, https://dataprotection.africa/wp-content/uploads/malabo_roadmap_Sept_2022.pdf.

²¹ <https://dataprotection.africa/wp-content/uploads/2305121.pdf>.

²² MUSWADA WA SHERIA YA ULINZI WA TAARIFA BINAFSI WA MWAKA 2022, MPANGILIO WA VIFUNGU SEHEMU YA KWANZA MASHARTI YA UTANGULIZI, Special Bill Supplement, No. 11, to the Special Gazette of the United Republic of Tanzania No.34. Vol. 103, Printed by the Government Printer, Dodoma by Order of Government, 31st August 2022, The United Republic of Tanzania, [http://www.parliament.go.tz/polis/uploads/bills/1664436755-document%20\(38\).pdf](http://www.parliament.go.tz/polis/uploads/bills/1664436755-document%20(38).pdf).

²³ African Union Convention on Cyber Security and Personal Data Protection, Preamble, https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/29560-treaty-0048_-_african_union_convention_on_cyber_security_and_personal_data_protection_e.pdf.

²⁴ AU Data Policy Framework, An Integrated, Prosperous and Peaceful Africa, Addis Ababa, February 2022, <https://au.int/sites/default/files/documents/42078-doc-AU-DATA-POLICY-FRAMEWORK-ENG1.pdf>.

6.1. AU CONVENTION ON CYBER SECURITY AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION (PREAMBLE)

Article 4: Advertising by Electronic Means²³

1. Without prejudice to Article 3 any advertising action, irrespective of its form, accessible through an online communication service, shall be clearly identified as such. It shall clearly identify the individual or corporate body on behalf of whom it is undertaken.

6. State Parties undertake to prohibit concealment of the identity of the person on whose behalf the advertisement accessed by an online communication service is issued.

Article 5: Electronic Contracts²³

1. The information requested for the purpose of concluding a contract or information available during contract execution may be transmitted by electronic means if the recipients have agreed to the use of that means. The use of electronic communications is presumed to be acceptable unless the recipient has previously expressly stated a preference for an alternative means of communication.

2. A service provider or supplier, who offers goods and services in a professional capacity by electronic means, shall make available the applicable contractual conditions directly or indirectly, in a way that facilitates the conservation and reproduction of such conditions according to national legislations.

3. For the contract to be validly concluded, the offeree shall have had the opportunity to verify details of his/her order, particularly the price thereof, prior to confirming the said order and signifying his/her acceptance.

6. a) Any natural or legal person engaged in the activity defined in the first paragraph of Article 2.1 of this Convention²³ shall, ipso facto, be accountable to his/her contractual partner for the proper performance of the obligations arising from the contract, irrespective of whether such obligations are to be carried out by himself/herself or by other service providers, without prejudice to his/her right to claim against the said service providers.

b) However, the natural or legal person may be released from all or part of the liability by proving that the non-fulfilment or poor performance of the contract is due either to the contractual partner or a case of force majeure.

Article 6: Writing in Electronic Form²³

1. Without prejudice to existing domestic legislative provisions in the State Party, no person shall be compelled to take legal action by electronic means.

a) Where a written document shall be required for the validity of a legal act each State Party shall establish the legal conditions for functional equivalence between electronic

communications and paper-based documents, when the internal regulations require a written document for the validity of a legal act.

b) Where a paper document has been subject to specific conditions as to legibility or presentation, the written document in electronic form shall be subject to the same conditions.

c) The requirement to transmit several copies of a written document shall be deemed to have been met in electronic form, where the said written document can be reproduced in material form by the addressee.

3. The delivery of a written document in electronic form shall be effective when the addressee takes due note and acknowledges receipt thereof.

4. Given their tax functions, invoices must be in writing to ensure the readability, integrity and sustainability of the content. The authenticity of the origin must also be guaranteed.

Among the methods that may be implemented to fulfil the tax purposes of the invoice and to ensure that its functions have been met is the establishment of management controls which create a reliable audit trail between an invoice and a supply of goods or services.

In addition to the type of controls described in § 1, the following methods are examples of technologies that ensure the authenticity of origin and integrity of content of an electronic invoice:

a) a qualified electronic signature as defined in Article 1²³;

b) electronic data interchange (EDI), understood as the electronic transfer, from computer to computer, of commercial and administrative data in the form of an EDI message structured according to an agreed standard, provided that the agreement to the exchange provides for the use of procedures guaranteeing the authenticity of the origin and data integrity.

5. A written document in electronic form is admissible in evidence in the same way as a paper-based document and shall have the same force of law provided that the person from whom it originates can be duly identified and that it has been made out and retained in a manner that guarantees its integrity.

Article 7: Ensuring the Security of Electronic Transactions²³

1. a) The supplier of goods shall allow his/her clients to make payments using electronic payment methods approved by the State according to the regulations in force in each State Party.

b) The supplier of goods or provider of services by electronic means who claims the discharge of an obligation must prove its existence or otherwise prove that the obligation was discharged or did not exist.

2. Where the legislative provisions of State Parties have not laid down other principles, and where there is no valid agreement between the parties, the judge shall resolve proof related conflicts by determining by all possible means the most plausible claim regardless of the message base employed.

3. a) A copy or any other reproduction of contracts signed by electronic means shall have the same probative value as the contract itself, where the said copy has been certified as a true copy of the said act by bodies duly accredited by an authority of the State Party.

b) Certification will result in the issuance, where necessary, of a certificate of conformity.

4. a) An electronic signature created by a secure device which the signatory is able to keep under his exclusive control and is appended to a digital certificate shall be admissible as signature on the same terms as a handwritten signature.

b) The reliability of the procedure is presumed, unless otherwise proven, if the electronic signature is generated by a secure signature creation device, the integrity of the act is guaranteed and the identification of the signatory is ensured.

Article 8: Objective of this Convention with Respect to Personal Data²³

1. Each State Party shall commit itself to establishing a legal framework aimed at strengthening fundamental rights and public freedoms, particularly the protection of physical data, and punish any violation of privacy without prejudice to the principle of free flow of personal data.

2. The mechanism so established shall ensure that any form of data processing respects the fundamental freedoms and rights of natural persons while recognizing the prerogatives of the State, the rights of local communities and the purposes for which the businesses were established.

Article 9: Scope of Application of the Convention²³

1. The following actions shall be subject to this Convention:

a) Any collection, processing, transmission, storage or use of personal data by a natural person, the State, local communities, and public or private corporate bodies;

b) Any automated or non-automated processing of data contained in or meant to be part of a file, with the exception of the processing defined in Article 9.2 of this Convention²³;

c) Any processing of data undertaken in the territory of a State Party;

d) Any processing of data relating to public security, defence, research, criminal prosecution or State security, subject to the exceptions defined by specific provisions of other extant laws.

2. This Convention shall not be applicable to:

- a) Data processing undertaken by a natural person within the exclusive context of his/her personal or household activities, provided however that such data are not for systematic communication to third parties or for dissemination;
- b) Temporary copies produced within the context of technical activities for transmission and access to a digital network with a view to automatic, intermediate and temporary storage of data and for the sole purpose of offering other beneficiaries of the service the best possible access to the information so transmitted.

Article 10: Preliminary personal data processing formalities²³

The following actions shall be exempted from the preliminary formalities:

- a) The processing mentioned in Article 9.2 of this Convention;
- b) Processing undertaken with the sole objective of maintaining a register meant exclusively for private use;
- c) Processing undertaken by a non-profit making association or body, with a religious, philosophical, political or trade union aim, provided that the data are consistent with the objective of the said association or body structure, and relate solely to its members, and that the data are not disclosed to a third party.

With the exception of the cases defined in Article 10.1 above and in Article 10.4 and 10.5 of this Convention, personal data processing shall be subject to a declaration before the protection authority.

With regard to the most common categories of personal data processing which are not likely to constitute a breach of privacy or individual freedoms, the protection authority may establish and publish standards with a view to simplifying or introducing exemptions from the obligation to make a declaration.

The following actions shall be undertaken after authorization by the national protection authority:

- a) Processing of personal data involving genetic information and health research;
- b) Processing of personal data involving information on offenses, convictions or security measures;
- c) Processing of personal data for the purpose of interconnection of files as defined in Article 15 of this Convention, data processing involving national identification number or any other identifier of the same type;

- d) Processing of personal data involving biometric data;
- e) Processing of personal data of public interest, particularly for historical, statistical or scientific purposes.

5. Personal data processing undertaken on behalf of the Government, a public institution, a local community, a private corporate body operating a public service, shall be in accordance with a legislative or regulatory act enacted after an informed advice of the protection authority.

Such data processing is related to:

- a) State security, defence or public security;
- b) Prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences, or execution of criminal convictions or security measures;
- c) Population survey;
- d) Personal data directly or indirectly revealing racial, ethnic or regional origin, affiliation, political, philosophical or religious beliefs or trade union membership of persons, or data concerning health or sex life.

6. Requests for opinion, declarations and applications for authorization shall indicate:

- a) The identity and address of the data controller or, where he/she is not established in the territory of a State Party of the African Union, the identity and address of his/her duly mandated representative;
- b) The purpose(s) of the processing and a general description of its functions;
- c) The interconnections envisaged or all other forms of harmonization with other processing activities;
- d) The personal data processed, their origin and the category of persons involved in the processing;
- e) Period of conservation of the processed data;
- f) The service or services responsible for carrying out the processing as well as the category of persons who, due to their functions or service requirements, have direct access to registered data;
- g) The recipients authorized to receive data communication;
- h) The function of the person or the service before which the right of access is to be exercised;

i) Measures taken to ensure the security of processing actions and of data; Indication regarding use of a sub-contractor;

k) Envisaged transfer of personal data to a third country that is not a member of the African Union, subject to reciprocity.

7. The national protection authority shall take a decision within a set timeframe starting from the date of receipt of the request for opinion or authorization.

Such timeframe may however be extended or not on the basis of an informed decision of the national protection authority.

8. The notification, the declaration or request for authorization may be addressed to the national protection authority by electronic means or by post.

9. The national protection authority may be approached by any person acting on his/her own, or through a lawyer or any other duly mandated natural or legal person.

Article 13: Basic Principles Governing the Processing of Personal Data²³

Principle 1: Principle of consent and legitimacy of personal data processing

Processing of personal data shall be deemed to be legitimate where the data subject has given his/her consent. This requirement of consent may however be waived where the processing is necessary for:

a) Compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject;

b) Performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller or in a third party to whom the data are disclosed;

c) Performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract;

d) Protect the vital interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject.

Principle 2: Principle of lawfulness and fairness of personal data processing

The collection, recording, processing, storage and transmission of personal data shall be undertaken lawfully, fairly and non-fraudulently.

Principle 3: Principle of purpose, relevance and storage of processed personal data

a) Data collection shall be undertaken for specific, explicit and legitimate purposes, and not further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes;

b) Data collection shall be adequate, relevant and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which they are collected and further processed;

c) Data shall be kept for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data were collected or further processed;

d) Beyond the required period, data may be stored only for the specific needs of data processing undertaken for historical, statistical or research purposes under the law.

Principle 4: Principle of accuracy of personal data

Data collected shall be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date. Every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that data which are inaccurate or incomplete, having regard to the purposes for which they were collected or for which they are further processed, are erased or rectified

Principle 5: Principle of transparency of personal data processing

The principle of transparency requires mandatory disclosure of information on personal data by the data controller.

Principle 6: Principle of confidentiality and security of personal data processing

a) Personal data shall be processed confidentially and protected, in particular where the processing involves transmission of the data over a network;

b) Where processing is undertaken on behalf of a controller, the latter shall choose a processor providing sufficient guarantees. It is incumbent on the controller and processor to ensure compliance with the security measures defined in this Convention.

Article 17: Right of Access²³

Any natural person whose personal data are to be processed may request from the controller, in the form of questions, the following:

a) Such information as would enable him/her to evaluate and object to the processing;

b) Confirmation as to whether or not data relating to him/her are being processed;

c) Communication to him/her of the personal data undergoing processing and any available information as to their source;

d) Information as to the purpose of the processing, the categories of personal data concerned, and the recipients or categories of recipients to whom the data are disclosed.

Article 18: Right to Object²³

Any natural person has the right to object, on legitimate grounds, to the processing of the data relating to him/her.

He/she shall have the right to be informed before personal data relating to him/her are disclosed for the first time to third parties or used on their behalf for the purposes

of marketing, and to be expressly offered the right to object, free of charge, to such disclosures or uses.

Article 19: Right of Rectification or Erasure²³

Any natural person may demand that the data controller rectify, complete, update, block or erase, as the case may be, the personal data concerning him/her where such data are inaccurate, incomplete, equivocal or out of date, or whose collection, use, disclosure or storage are prohibited.

Article 20: Confidentiality obligations²³

Processing of personal data shall be confidential. Such processing shall be undertaken solely by persons operating under the authority of a data controller and only on instructions from the controller.

Article 21: Security obligations²³

The data controller must take all appropriate precautions, according to the nature of the data, and in particular, to prevent such data from being altered or destroyed, or accessed by unauthorized third parties.

Article 22: Storage obligations²³

Personal data shall be kept for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data were collected or processed.

Article 23: Sustainability obligations²³

a) The data controller shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that processed personal data can be utilized regardless of the technical device employed in the process.

b) The processing official shall, in particular, ensure that technological changes do not constitute an obstacle to the said utilization.

Article 26: National cyber security system²³

1. Culture of Cyber Security

a) Each State Party undertakes to promote the culture of cyber security among all stakeholders, namely, governments, enterprises and the civil society, which develop, own, manage, operationalize and use information systems and networks. The culture of cyber security should lay emphasis on security in the development of information systems and networks, and on the adoption of new ways of thinking and behaving

when using information systems as well as during communication or transactions across networks.

b) As part of the promotion of the culture of cyber security, State Parties may adopt the following measures: establish a cyber-security plan for the systems run by their governments; elaborate and implement programmes and initiatives for sensitization on security for systems and networks users; encourage the development of a cybersecurity culture in enterprises; foster the involvement of the civil society; launch a comprehensive and detailed national sensitization programme for internet users, small business, schools and children.

3. Public-Private Partnership

Each State Party shall develop public-private partnership as a model to engage industry, the civil society, and academia in the promotion and enhancement of a culture of cyber security.

4. Education and Training

Each State Party shall adopt measures to develop capacity building with a view to offering training which covers all areas of cyber security to different stakeholders and setting standards for the private sector.

States Parties undertake to promote technical education for information and communication technology professionals, within and outside government bodies, through certification and standardization of training; categorization of professional qualifications as well as development and needs-based distribution of educational material.

Article 28: International Cooperation²³

1. Harmonization

State Parties shall ensure that the legislative measures and/or regulations adopted to fight against cyber-crime will strengthen the possibility of regional harmonization of these measures and respect the principle of double criminal liability.

2. Mutual legal assistance

State Parties that do not have agreements on mutual assistance in cyber-crime shall undertake to encourage the signing of agreements on mutual legal assistance in conformity with the principle of double criminal liability, while promoting the exchange of information as well as the efficient sharing of data between the organizations of State Parties on a bilateral and multilateral basis.

2. Exchange of information

State Parties shall encourage the establishment of institutions that exchange information on cyber threats and vulnerability assessment such as the Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT) or the Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs).

3. Means of cooperation

State Parties shall make use of existing means for international cooperation with a view to responding to cyber threats, improving cyber security and stimulating dialogue between stakeholders. These means may be international, intergovernmental or regional, or based on private and public partnerships.

Article 32: Measures to be taken at the level of the African Union²³

The Chairperson of the Commission shall report to the Assembly on the establishment and monitoring of the operational mechanism for this Convention.

The monitoring mechanism to be established shall ensure the following:

- a) Promote and encourage the Continent to adopt and implement measures to strengthen cyber security in electronic services and in combatting cybercrime and human rights violations in cyberspace;
- b) Gather documents and information on cyber security needs as well as on the nature and magnitude of cybercrime and human rights violations in cyberspace;
- c) Work out methods for analysing cyber security needs, as well as the nature and magnitude of cybercrime and human rights violations in cyberspace, disseminate information and sensitize the public on the negative effects of these phenomena;
- d) Advise African governments on the way to promote cyber security and combat the scourge of cybercrime and human rights violations in cyberspace at national level;
- e) Garner information and carry out analyses of the criminal behaviour of the users of information networks and computer systems operating in Africa, and transmit such information to competent national authorities;
- f) Formulate and promote the adoption of harmonized codes of conduct for the use of public officials in the area of cyber security;
- g) Establish partnerships with the Commission and the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights, the African civil society, and governmental, intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations with a view to facilitating dialogue on combating cybercrime and human rights violations in cyberspace;
- h) Submit regular reports to the Executive Council of the African Union on the progress made by each State Party in the implementation of the provisions of this Convention;
- i) Carry out any other tasks relating to cybercrime and breaches of the rights of individuals in cyberspace as may be assigned to it by the policy organs of the African Union.

Article 34: Settlement of Disputes²³

1. Any dispute arising from this Convention shall be settled amicably through direct negotiations between the State Parties concerned.
2. Where the dispute cannot be resolved through direct negotiation, the State Parties shall endeavour to resolve the dispute through other peaceful means, including good offices, mediation and conciliation, or any other peaceful means agreed upon by the State Parties. In this regard, the State Parties shall be encouraged to make use of the procedures and mechanisms for resolution of disputes established within the framework of the Union.

6.2. AU DATA POLICY FRAMEWORK

5.3.2.5. DATA ETHICS²⁴

An important way to reduce risk and mitigate harm through the application of new data technologies is through contextually appropriate data ethics. Codes of ethics should be developed by all stakeholder groups working with data, including researchers, industry associations and data experts. These codes of ethics are valuable for guiding the use of data and the processes of designing and implementing data systems, including embedding them in computer code in the case of developing algorithms.

However, codes of ethics have been criticised as representing the views of limited demographics, mostly defined by corporations and technologists. Ethical codes can also relieve corporations of regulatory accountability when used as a form of self-regulation and can be insufficient in enabling the fundamental rights of people when using technology.

Working together enables trustworthy data systems by providing the kind of practical and technical details that support laws since the latter are usually of more general application than specific ethical codes but also sometimes less quickly adaptable to new technologies. Ethics operate prospectively, enabling ethical design, while laws tend to be enacted and operate retrospectively. Ethical codes of conduct should embody digital rights and support compliance with international and national law.

The AU supports efforts to make ethical codes more inclusive through processes that take into account the voices of citizens, consumers, marginalised and underrepresented people. Nevertheless, mechanisms for ensuring adherence to ethical codes, as well as for updating those codes, are underdeveloped.

Human rights treaties – as the product of consensus processes between the legitimate representatives of citizens – enjoy greater legitimacy than codes of ethics and are legally enforceable when enacted at the national level and through regional adjudication. While these treaties sometimes do not have the specificity necessary for data ecosystems, digital rights, which have been formulated variously by civil society amongst others and draw on the human rights framework, provide the kind of specificity that can be drawn on. Although

existing human rights bodies and adjudicators have the requisite capacity to develop rights in response to data issues, their legal mandates may not sufficiently empower them to do so.

Recommendations:

- Member States should encourage the development and adherence to codes of ethics that are responsive to the African context and which promote digital and human rights. This means people who work with data, regardless of the sector they work in, must respect rights and adhere to these ethical standards. These codes ought to take note of gender considerations within the African context, ensuring they reduce harm and exclusion of women and girls. It is impractical for member states to legislate that all technologies and technology providers dealing with data adhere to particular ethical codes since many of these technologies are designed, built and operated in other jurisdictions. Member States should, however, encourage the adoption of these codes of ethics by themselves, making use only of technologies and technology providers that adhere to approved codes of ethical conduct.
- Besides any regulatory or judicial legal recourse available in a country, there is also scope to consider empowering existing human rights mechanisms at the national, regional and continental levels to adjudicate uses of data.

Actions:

- The data industry and research communities using data need to formulate and implement codes of practice, including the principles of responsibility and ethics by design through processes that include those whose data is affected.
- Member States must require rights-compliant ethical frameworks in public procurement processes.
- Members should include the assessment of data codes of ethics in the mandates of existing human rights bodies such as Human Rights Commissions.

5.4.2. DATA PROCESSING AND PROTECTION²⁴

Defining the problem

While data control principles help to outline delineation and obligations in respect of both personal and non-personal data, data processing seeks to outline the policy guidelines for the processing of personal data, as discussed earlier. Regulation of non-personal data is determined by data categorisation and specific access regimes.

These forms of guidance are important as a mechanism for realising privacy and data protection. Personal data processing is a critical component of data governance and fostering a trusting environment. The building of trust is understood as a necessary part of fostering a sound data and digital economy. By constraining process limitations to personal data, such constraints need not impede the data flows for digital trade; but to ensure such lack of

impediment requires consistent data policies across the region based on shared but flexible principles (United Nations, 2017²⁵).

As an aspect of personal data processing, data subject rights also offer ancillary benefits for helping to ensure data integrity and quality.

A privacy-by-design approach can be taken when developing digital technologies and systems by which privacy is incorporated into technology and systems by default during the design and development process (Cavoukian, 2009²⁶). For instance, it may entrench minimality in its data collection or automate rigid de-identification. It means a product is designed with privacy as a priority, along with whatever other purposes the system serves. This design should incorporate a particular understanding of how data subjects engage with products and their capabilities for asserting their privacy.

De-identification techniques, including anonymisation and pseudonymisation, can facilitate some uses of data while providing at least partial data protection. Pseudonymisation can be accomplished through the use of a signifier or mask that can only be connected to an identifiable individual through additional data. While both anonymisation and pseudonymisation may enable both private service providers and the public sector to make greater use of data, they are reliant on the current state of technology and mathematics. As new mathematical approaches are developed, and computer processing power increases, data that was deemed de-identified may become identifiable. While data protection regulations often require de-identification, these techniques are insufficient without strong legal rights for data subjects and a regulator with the capacity to enforce data protection.

Actions:

- Data processing frameworks should be established in partnership with all relevant multi-stakeholder partners but driven ideally by the Data Protection Act (DPA). These should align with the following principles: consent and legitimacy; limitations on collection; purpose specification; use limitation; data quality; security safeguards; openness (including incident reporting, an important correlation to cybersecurity and cybercrime imperatives); accountability; and data specificity.

²⁵ United Nations. (2017). Looking to future, UN to consider how artificial intelligence could help achieve economic growth and reduce inequalities—United Nations Sustainable Development. <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/blog/2017/10/looking-to-future-un-to-consider-how-artificial-intelligence-could-help-achieve-economic-growth-and-reduce-inequalities/>

²⁶ Cavoukian, A. (2009). Privacy by design. The 7 foundational principles. Implementation and mapping of fair information practices. Information and Privacy Commissioner.

- DPAs should be established as a matter of urgency alongside national legislation on personal data protection.

5.4.3 DATA ACCESS AND INTEROPERABILITY²⁴

Data access and accessibility are understood both in terms of reactive forms of access facilitated by laws and regulations, as well as through proactive forms of data access (such as through open government data) (Open Data Charter, 2015²⁷). Accessibility also implicates sharing of data across agents or departments, an important benefit of data's non-rivalrous nature. Yet this requires interoperability between these different agents (Jones & Tonetti, 2020²⁸). In the context of competition, data is not simply portable in a way that can facilitate scale effects easily between firms (Rinehart, 2020²⁹). Requiring forms of data portability remains a key cited regulatory strategy for facilitating competition and consumer benefit, though the realities have not yet been established as definitively beneficial (Mitretoadis & Euper, 2019³⁰; Rinehart, 2020²⁹). From a privacy perspective, outside of just interoperability changes, the nature of big data collection means that data portability implicates other users' privacy (Nicholas & Weinberg, 2019³¹).

Recommendations:

- DPAs must be established that are independent, funded and effective. Additionally, as a method of ensuring effectiveness, accountability metrics are crucial for helping a DPA have a clear scope. Lawful data processing frameworks must be established, including clear deterring penalties to ensure compliance. They must cover all relevant data processing actors.
- Personal data risk assessment should be obliged in the deployment of personal data technology development.

²⁷ Open Data Charter. (2015). Open Data Charter Principles. Open Data Charter. <https://open-datacharter.net/principles/>

²⁸ Jones, C., & Tonetti, C. (2020). Nonrivalry and the Economics of Data. *The American Economic Review*, 110(9), 2819–2858. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.20191330>

²⁹ Rinehart, W. (2020, September 14). Is data nonrivalrous? Medium. <https://medium.com/cgo-benchmark/is-data-nonrivalrous-f1c8e720820b>

³⁰ Mitretoadis, & Euper. (2019). Interaction Between Privacy and Competition Law in a Digital Economy. *Competition Chronicle*. <https://www.competitionchronicle.com/2019/07/interaction-between-privacy-and-competition-law-in-a-digital-economy/>

³¹ Nicholas, G., & Weinberg, M. (2019). Data Portability and Platform Competition: Is User Data Exported From Facebook Actually Useful to Competitors? | NYU School of Law. New York University School of Law. <https://www.law.nyu.edu/centers/engelberg/pubs/2019-11-06-Data-Portability-And-Platform-Competition>

- An important sub-principle, which must be actioned with data processing frameworks for public and private stakeholders, is that of minimisation. The minimisation of personal data collection is one of the most effective mechanisms for mitigating data subject risks and harms.
- Codes of Conduct should be explored to promote data and sector-specific needs. Such Codes, approved by the relevant DPA, can provide sector and industry expertise in managing the real risks and harms associated with processing and ensuring best practices in the management of those harms. It can also help to consider the sectoral exceptions required for a constructive data economy to thrive but also feed into a broader Sustainable Development agenda, such as through the ready facilitation of research (in health or other social development arenas).

Actions:

- Member States should establish an open data policy which sets open standards for the production and processing of data so that when decisions are made to open the data, the high costs of ensuring it is usable and manipulatable are avoided.
- Sectoral laws and codes of conduct from DPAs should be reviewed to ensure lawful data access in conjunction with the data policy.
- DPAs should have dual access to information and privacy function.
- Multi-sectoral open data initiatives should be implemented in priority data sectors like health, research and planning.

5.4.4. Data Security²⁴

Defining the problem

Data security includes the set of policies, norms, regulations, legislation and practices to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data from unauthorised access, corruption or theft throughout the entire lifecycle of data. These fundamental principles of data security also define the three main areas of accountability of information security. The concept of data security encompasses many aspects, from the physical security of data centre hardware and storage devices to administrative access controls, as well as the logical security of networks, software, and applications. It also includes organisational procedures and policies.

Recommendations:

- Open data standards should be prioritised in public data creation and maintenance. The creation of data to these standards does not preclude overlaid mechanisms for control or limiting access in defined data categories for compelling purposes.
- Data portability should be supported. Data portability can be a form of data subject right, defined as the right of the data subject to obtain data that a data controller holds

on them in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and to re-use it for their own purposes. Portability can be facilitated through a policy on data portability in public sector data and by establishing specific data portability rights in consumer contexts.

- Data partnerships (including options like databanks) should be prioritised as mechanisms for advancing quality and privacy-preserving open data.
- As a method of facilitating specificity, data categorisation can be a method for ensuring cohesion within data processing frameworks within processing allowances and security principles. The categorisation referred to here is not such as the sectoral typologies considered more broadly but rather as a specific mechanism for realising particularly forms of risks that align to data and information types and might include sensitive categories (such as children’s data), security classifications of relevance, as compared to forms of data already in the public domain.
- Restrictions on processing need to be clearly articulated and limited in order to not interfere with low-risk processing that might be increasingly central to the training of AI through large-scale data processing.

Confidentiality, integrity, and data availability, from a regulatory perspective, depend on national cybersecurity policies and legislation. The security of data (including confidentiality, integrity and availability) also does not depend on the physical location of the servers hosting such data. Rather, it is a function of the normative rules – including norms, policies, regulations, laws and protocols (such as data standards and technical interfaces), and the implementation of technologies and security measures (such as encryption, firewalls and access controls) – that are put in place by public or private service providers in the way that they store, access, share and use the data.

Increasing data security legislation and technical measures may both improve confidentiality, integrity and availability (positive security) as well as undermine fundamental freedom and rights of privacy, dignity, and safety online (negative security). For example, some countries may impose restrictions on data sharing and transfer by enacting cybersecurity legislation to protect users’ data safety and security. These can be barriers to the free flow of data. From a cybersecurity perspective, some states may believe that data is more secure if it is stored within national borders. States may erroneously refer to it as principles of data sovereignty, while these measures are simply forms of data protectionism and data localisation.

A principle that is difficult to uphold with regard to data security is that of transparency. While countries continue to witness an increase in the number of attacks reported to law enforcement, improvements in this area have been driven almost entirely by data protection regulations, and reported incidents are primarily data breaches. On the other hand, increasing transparency on data security includes both technical aspects, such as reporting on zero-day vulnerabilities and adherence to international cybersecurity standards, as well as policy aspects related to the assessment of cyber capacity maturity. Transparency in data security

has the potential to improve technical and procedural defence mechanisms against attacks and to strengthen collaborative practices based on information sharing.

Recommendations:

- Member States should develop national cyber security policies as well as necessary legal and technical measures to sustain trust in their digital space.
- Member States are encouraged to co-operate regionally to develop cybersecurity standards to be met in both the public and private sectors to increase regional economic growth.
- Data policies should align with cybersecurity and cybercrime policies, and legislation dealing with cybercrime should respect human rights.
- A joint sanction regime for cyber-attacks should be established.

Actions:

- Member States, who are yet to develop cybersecurity measures, should immediately develop cybersecurity plans and streamline them within government governance structures to promote robustness and reduce vulnerabilities.
- Cybersecurity institutions like CSIRTs should be incorporated into data policy development.
- Data processing roles as a form of security protection should be specified in policy by policymakers.
- Capacity-building in relation to data protection, cybersecurity and institutional data governance in relevant agencies should be assured through policy and asset allocation and could be supported by DPAs.

5.4.5. Cross-Border Data Flows²⁴

An increasingly important issue regarding international and regional trade is the cross-border transfer of personal and other data (Deloitte, 2017³²). In the African context, international and regional frameworks that facilitate cross-border transactions and personal data flow across countries are essential for the creation of common markets and particularly for the realisation of the African Free Trade Area. Cross-border data transfer of personal data, in particular, is

³² Deloitte. (2017). Privacy is Paramount | Personal Data Protection in Africa Personal Data Protection in Africa. Deloitte. https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/za/Documents/risk/Personal_Data_Protection_in_Africa.pdf za_Privacy_is_Paramount-

shaped by the data sovereignty approach that a country wants to pursue, which refers to the legal principle that information (generally in electronic form) is regulated or governed by the legal regime of the country in which that data resides. As noted, this concept is challenged by the modern reality of data movements. Critiques of the supposed ‘data flows’ narrative and the extent of its benefits for digital dividends in development should however be acknowledged, as should recognition that significant amounts of data flows actually occur horizontally within firms rather than between firms (UNCTAD, 2021³³).

It is also worth mentioning the common position that the transfer of data is dependent on whether the receiving country has an adequate level of protection (Razzano et al., 2020³⁴). However, what amounts to this ‘adequate’ level will frequently be determined by a country’s Data Protection Authority or similar. Thus, in the absence of a data protection law in the receiving country, the transfer of personal data cannot be subject to proper regulation unless the law of a country forbids the transfer of data except to a country with an adequate level of protection, or through the establishment of bilateral obligations through contracts between the transferring parties.

The reality is that broad limitations on cross-border data transfer could result in business opportunities lost and reduce the ability of an organisation to trade internationally, leading to a reduced geographical footprint and loss of market competitiveness. Data regulation that is synchronous with regulations in other jurisdictions contributes to mutual trust and lays a foundation for a trusted exchange of data, including (but not limited to) personal data. In this sense, personal data protection regulation enables and improves trust and trade in the cross-border movement of persons, goods and services (Information Society, 2018³⁵).

Recommendations:

- Data protection frameworks should provide minimum standards for cross-border data flows.
- The establishment of norms and standards should expressly ensure reciprocity as a central principle for permitting cross border flows.

³³ UNCTAD. (2021). Digital Economy Report 2021: Cross-Border Data Flows and Development: For Whom the Data Flow [United Nations publication].

³⁴ Razzano, G., Gillwald, A., Aguera, P., Ahmed, S., Calandro, E., Matanga, C., Rens, A., & van der Spuy, A. (2020). SADC Parliamentary Forum Discussion Paper: The Digital Economy and Society. Research ICT Africa. <https://researchictafrica.net/publication/sadc-pf-discussion-pa-per-the-digital-economy-and-society/>

³⁵ Information Society. (2018). Personal Data Protection Guidelines for Africa. A joint initiative of the Internet Society and the Commission of the African Union. https://www.internetsociety.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/AUCPrivacyGuidelines_2018508_EN.pdf

- Data specificity should be prioritised to avoid unintended restrictions on productive data sharing.
- Law enforcement considerations should be incorporated into the policy-making process.
- To ensure effective cross-border resolution, a degree of capacity must be ensured across agencies.
- Members of the African Union should rigorously define a framework and modalities to regulate cross borders data flows and identify the African entity and persons entitled to manage this system.

5.5. International and Regional Governance²⁴

At a transnational and continental level - particularly to provide capability for cybersecurity and to address data protection concerns associated with the changes in data economics - cooperation between countries is of increasing significance. The scope of cooperation needed includes dialogue between governments, collaboration with the private sector, and effective, integrated processes to investigate and prosecute cross-border breaches. A global trust architecture that accounts for the limitations of existing national or otherwise fragmented systems is essential to secure a digital economy and digital inclusion (African Development Bank 2019³⁶).

Certain international and continental-wide initiatives serve as a foundational step for precipitating implementation. For instance, the African Union and regional initiatives on digitally encoded genetic data³⁷ and geographical and environmental data, respectively. The

³⁶ African Development Bank. (2019). Annual Report 2019 | African Development Bank—Building today, a better Africa tomorrow. <https://www.afdb.org/en/documents/annual-report-2019>

³⁷ While the category of digitally encoded genetic data includes the genetic data of humans, where these are identifiable individuals this should be regarded as sensitive data and dealt with as required by the Malabo convention. But there are other kinds of digitally encoded genetic data that require specific/special treatment that are neither sensitive nor personal. These include demographic genetic data, and the genetic data of organisms other than humans. The African Union is currently engaging with other countries who are parties to the Convention on Biodiversity (CBD) to ensure that digitally encoded data should be treated as biological resources as that term is used in the CBD. The convention states that biological resources "include genetic resources, organisms or parts thereof, populations, or any other biotic component of ecosystems with actual or potential use or value for humanity". The convention governs both access and benefit sharing to both enable research and to require that people who are custodians of biodiversity share in the benefits of that research. Applying the rules of the convention will enable beneficial data flow while also ensuring that Africans benefit.

African Union Commission will ensure harmony between these initiatives and the ongoing data policy work³⁸.

Recommendations:

The African Union, with the support of sister Pan African organisations, should:

- Facilitate collaboration between the various entities dealing with data across the continent through the establishment of a consultation framework within the digital ecosystem community to safeguard the interest of each actor.
- Strengthen links with other regions and coordinate Africa's common positions on data related international negotiations to ensure equal opportunities in the global digital economy.
- Support the development of regional and continental data infrastructure to host advanced data-driven technologies (such as Big Data, Machine learning and Artificial Intelligence) and the necessary enabling environment and data-sharing mechanism to ensure circulation across the continent.

5.5.1. Continental Data Standards²⁴

To facilitate cross-border cooperation, it is important to achieve consensus on data standards, which is an integral consideration for advancing interoperability. These multistakeholder forms of consensus should reference the work done through the International Organisation for Standardisation and other forms of international consensus achieved in specific sectoral contexts. However, while international standardisation is important for competitiveness, it should be noted that these international standards may not be sufficient for the region's needs. This is demonstrated, for instance, in language challenges found in the context of spatial or geographical data.

5.5.2. Open Data Portal and Other Initiatives²⁴

There are important open data initiatives already occurring centrally, which should remain supported in the name of a sound regional data economy. These include the African

³⁸ The Regional Data Strategy for Marine and Coastal Areas Management in Western Africa promotes more sustainable management of natural resources through mutual sharing of data.

Development Bank's central open-data portal³⁹, and institutionally driven initiatives⁴⁰ and volunteer-driven communities⁴¹.

5.5.3 Continental Instruments²⁴

The broad range of existing relevant instruments are outlined in section 4. However, two specific areas need to be highlighted.

Cross-border data flow mechanism

There is an opportunity to leverage this framework to begin collaboration towards a regional cross-border data flow mechanism facilitated by an overarching instrument, such as those by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN).

AU Convention on Cybersecurity and Personal Data Protection

It is recommended that the AU Convention be ratified as soon as possible to serve as the foundational step for the harmonisation of data processing. Additional protocols to the Convention should also be explored to reflect changes since the original drafting.

African Continental Free Trade Agreement

The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) provides an opportunity for cooperation on a number of important aspects of the Data policy framework, most saliently in the development of the agreements on competition, intellectual property and investment.

5.5.4. Continental and Regional Institutions and Associations²⁴

Regional institutions and associations create a central mechanism for creating a unified regional voice on data issues. Many associations already exist, and ensuring the implementation of this framework speaks to existing associations is a priority recommendation. Continental and regional bodies are particularly important due to the cross-border nature of data flow required to benefit from data.

Regional economic and development communities

³⁹ <https://dataportal.opendataforafrica.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.datafirst.uct.ac.za/dataportal/index.php/catalog/central/about>

⁴¹ <https://africaopendata.org/>

The Regional Economic Communities, as building blocks of the African Union can assist member states to create capacity, domesticate data policy and reach consensus on harmonisation of data policy, participate in standards making, and enable data flow.

Human rights adjudicators

The African Court on Human and People’s Rights, the East African Court of Justice, and the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) Community Court of Justice provide for a skilled capacity to adjudicate complex disputes on privacy and equality, which are relevant to personal data protection and the use of data to unfairly discriminate.

The South African Development Community (SADC) Tribunal, once recapacitated, could also offer a forum for data disputes, albeit within a more limited mandate. Continental and regional adjudication mechanisms are best placed to resolve cross-border data disputes.

African Network of Data Regulators

Empowering DPAs and improving the level of enforcement of legislative and regulatory frameworks at national level significantly assist individual’s enjoyment of digital rights. An avenue for this capacitation is through the promotion and support of existing associations, such as the African Network of Data Protection Authorities.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) regulatory authority associations

There are existing ICT associations, such as the Regional Association of Regulators (ART-AC, WATRA, CRASA and EACO), that stand as important mechanisms for peer learning on cross-border associations. They can also facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing as cross-border instruments and standards are explored.

Sectoral associations

Sectoral associations like the African Tax Administration Forum will be needed to help realise data economy recommendations areas in particular. Given the importance of digital identity within the data economy, the Association of National Registrars is also important.

African Competition Forum

The African Competition Forum (ACF) describes itself as “an informal network of African national and multinational competition authorities”. The ACF can create capacity for competition authorities to better regulate data issues.

6.3. THE MALABO ROADMAP

It outlines a Roadmap to advance legal frameworks for data protection and cybercrime in Africa. It aims to guide a process of public discussion on bringing into force the African Union (AU) Convention on Cyber Security and Personal Data Protection, 2014 (the Malabo

Convention or the Convention²⁰) as a continental framework to advance data protection and privacy in the region.

Overview²⁰

4. The Malabo Convention was initially drafted in 2011 to establish a “credible framework for cybersecurity in Africa through [the] organisation of electronic transactions, protection of personal data, promotion of cyber security, e-governance, and combating cybercrime.” The adoption of the Malabo Convention was postponed several times after earlier versions of the document faced criticism from the private sector, civil society organisations, and advocates for digital rights and freedoms.² The draft Malabo Convention was reviewed by an AU-convened meeting of experts in May 2014, before being redrafted and finally adopted in June 2014. Since then, AU member states have been slow to ratify the Malabo Convention, although as of 25 March 2022, thirteen states have ratified it, bringing it close to the fifteen ratifications needed to bring it into operation (Annex I).

Electronic transactions²⁰

6. While the Malabo Convention’s provisions on electronic transactions are less relevant for the purposes of this Roadmap, in brief, the Convention provides a set of harmonised standards and rules on various forms of e-commerce, including electronic advertising, the status of electronic contracts, and payment security for electronic transactions (Articles 3-7²³).

Data protection²⁰

7. The Malabo Convention mandates every state to establish a data protection framework, “aimed at strengthening fundamental rights and public freedoms, particularly the protection of physical data, and to punish any violation of privacy without prejudice to the principle of the free flow of information” (Article 8(1)²³). This framework is to be monitored and enforced by a national DPA with administrative independence, and a duty to ensure that the processing of personal data is duly regulated (Article 11²³). Each state’s framework for the processing of personal information should align with core data protection principles, such as consent, lawfulness, confidentiality, and transparency (Article 13²³), with various rights conferred on every person concerning the protection of their data (Article 16-19²³).

Prevailing approaches to continental data protection frameworks²⁰

11. In the years since the passage of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁵ of the European Union (EU), the prevailing view in many policy circles has been toward regional frameworks on data protection. In the global context, the GDPR has been crucial in advancing and harmonising data protection principles in the world’s biggest single market and establishing a benchmark for data protection regulation internationally. By dint of its place within the EU, one of the world’s biggest economies, the GDPR also presents an imperative for other countries and international industries to establish equivalent data protection measures. In the African context, the case for a continental framework for data protection includes meeting these imperatives, but it should also be viewed in the context of the

domestic and continental demand for domestic data protection regimes in Africa, which would further enable regional trade and economic development.

12. Despite what has been criticised as slow progress, there have been significant advances within the region in recent years. As of July 2022, 33 countries in Africa had enacted fully dedicated data protection legislation — a significant improvement in the past decade. However, 22 African countries did not have data protection laws in place. Many of those countries with data protection laws continue to face significant hurdles to implementation, low levels of transparency, and a lack of institutional independence⁴².

14. Cross-border data flows are a significant consideration in the economic case for regional data protection frameworks. Data localisation — policies and laws to restrict the flow of data across borders — may in certain contexts uphold important data protection principles, but cumbersome or overbroad restrictions on the transfer of data across national borders come at a severe cost to economic development, job creation, and global competitiveness⁴³. Notably, several policy analyses have observed a trend towards data localisation and nationalisation in African jurisdictions⁴⁴. A regional or continental data protection framework offers a harmonised approach to enabling cross-border data transfers between member states, while providing standards and safeguards for data protection principles⁴⁴.

15. While global data protection policy trends lean towards regional frameworks, this approach is not without criticism. In observing the early years of implementation of the GDPR since it entered force in 2018, the most common criticisms centre on cost, complexity, and implementation. EU authorities continue to grapple with the harmonisation of member states' data protection laws, and have, in particular, struggled to deal effectively with crossborder cases — a key mechanism to align data protection principles with crossborder data flows⁴⁵. A study on the implementation of the GDPR in ten countries found that most of the national adaptations are still incomplete and may not fully conform with the GDPR⁴⁶. The significant

⁴² Paradigm Initiative, Data Protection Authorities in Africa (DPAS) Report, 2021, <https://paradigmhq.org/report/data-protection-authorities-in-africa-dpas-report/>

⁴³ Atabey, 'The Potential Economic Empowering Role of Cross-border Data Flows for Data Protection in Africa' in Sampath Tregenna (eds), *Digital Sovereignty: African Perspectives*, University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg, 2022 at 24.

⁴⁴ Kugler, 'The Impact of data localisation laws on trade in Africa' Policy Brief 8 The Mandela Institute, School of Law, University of the Witwatersrand, 2021.

⁴⁵ European Commission, 'Data protection as a pillar of citizens' empowerment and the EU's approach to the digital transition — two years of application of the General Data Protection Regulation', COM 2020 264, June 2020 at 5.

⁴⁶ McCullagh, Tambou and Bourton (eds), *National Adaptations of the GDPR*, Collection Open Access Book, Blogdroiteuropeen, Luxembourg, 2019.

cost of GDPR compliance has also been noted.⁴⁷ However, it should be noted that a key argument for regional data protection frameworks is that, by creating harmonised policy across a range of markets, a regional approach seeks ultimately to simplify compliance and reduce costs.

The influence of European policy²⁰

30. While it is not clear how widely this view is held, certain analyses have argued that the Malabo Convention — and many national-level approaches to data protection and cyber policy in Africa — reflect external pressure and internal tendencies in African societies to import or approximate European data protection regimes⁴⁸, if they are fit for purpose. It is also correctly argued that African laws and policies on privacy and data protection must be shaped by local norms and values. It is important to note, though, that the idea that notions of privacy and data protection are incompatible with predominant cultural values in African societies has largely been debunked and that African-centric conceptions of privacy can and should be advanced⁴⁹.

31. Importantly, an argument that data protection approaches in Africa, both at a national level and in the Malabo Convention itself, reflect Western hegemony may be redundant: the more compelling case is that a harmonised continent framework in Africa, whatever its inspiration, will strengthen Africa's position in the global domain — both in relation to powerful economies like the United States (US), Europe, and China, and in relation to dominant technology companies in the West and Asia⁵⁰. It has been argued that the policy inertia which has stalled ratification and implementation of the Malabo Convention has left many African countries in holding patterns “that are essentially set by companies originating from China, the US, and the EU”⁵¹.

⁴⁷ Chen, Frey and Presidente, 'Privacy Regulation and Firm Performance: Estimating the GDPR Effect Globally', The Oxford Martin Working Paper Series on Technological and Economic Change (Working Paper No. 2022-1), January 2022.

⁴⁸ Bryant, 'Africa in the Information Age: Challenges, Opportunities, and Strategies for Data Protection and Digital Rights', Stanford Technology Law Review, Vol. 24:2, 2021 at 417.

⁴⁹ See, for example, Makulilo, "One size fits all": Does Europe impose its data protection regime on Africa?' *Datenschutz und Datensicherheit* 7, 2013.

⁵⁰ See stakeholder remarks in Center for Global Development, 'Are Current Models of Data Protection Fit for Purpose? Understanding the Consequences for Economic Development' CDG Brief, 2021, <https://www.cgdev.org/publication/are-current-models-data-protection-fit-purpose-understanding-consequences-economic>.

⁵¹ Ayodele, 'Big Tech: Not-so-Simple Politics' in Gehl Sampath and Tregenna (eds), *Digital Sovereignty: African Perspectives*, University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg, 2022 at 103.

The Smart Africa Alliance²⁰

38. Launched in 2013, the Smart Africa Alliance (Smart Africa) is an alliance of 32 African countries, international organisations, and global private sector actors tasked with advancing Africa's digital agenda. Smart Africa brings together heads of state who seek to accelerate the digitalisation of the continent and create a common market and has already undertaken several strategic initiatives to advance data protection and cybersecurity policy and implementation across Africa. These include:

38.1. Capacity-building and development of data protection authorities: In March 2022, Smart Africa and the NADPA/RAPDP signed a memorandum of understanding to support authorities' enforcement and harmonisation of personal data protection laws⁵².

38.2. Developing a Pan-African framework on data protection and privacy: After forming a Data Protection Working Group in support of states' efforts to develop data protection strategies and policies, in March 2021 Smart Africa announced a project to develop a Pan-African framework on data protection and privacy⁵³, which it aims to put into operation within three years. This initiative appears to be aimed at identifying the harmonisation challenges between different national and regional frameworks and developing strategies to address policy conflicts, improve the implementation and enforcement of data protection frameworks, and improve the capacity of DPAs.

38.3. Developing a cybersecurity blueprint for Africa: Similarly, in March 2022 Smart Africa announced a project to develop a cybersecurity blueprint for Africa, seeking to harmonise cybersecurity frameworks on the continent and develop institutions and processes to enhance regional cooperation on cybercrime⁵⁴.

The AU Data Policy Framework²⁰

39. In addition to Smart Africa's Pan-African Framework and blueprint, the African Union Commission, supported by Research ICT Africa (RIA), has developed the AU Data Policy Framework for Africa²⁴. The Framework sets out "a common vision, principles, strategic priorities and key recommendations to guide African Union Member States in developing

⁵² RAPDP, 'Smart Africa et NADPA/RAPDP ont signé un protocole d'accord pour faire progresser l'application et l'harmonisation des lois sur la protection des données personnelles en Afrique', 13 March 2022, <https://www.rapdp.org/fr/actualites/smart-africa-et-nadparapdp-ont-signé-un-protocole-d'accord-pour-faire-progresser>.

⁵³ Smart Africa, 'Request for proposals for the recruitment of a consultancy firm to draft a Pan-African framework on data protection and privacy' 24 March 2021, https://smartafrica.org/?post_type=job_listing&p=5176.

⁵⁴ Smart Africa, 'Recruitment of a consultancy firm to develop a continental blueprint for the Cybersecurity Project for Africa' 11 March 2022, https://smartafrica.org/?post_type=job_listing&p=5842.

their national data systems and capabilities to effectively derive value from data that is being generated by citizens, government entities and industries.”

40. The Framework follows a recommendation in the AU Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa⁵⁵ and “builds on a range of existing initiatives and frameworks including the Policy and Regulatory Initiative for Digital Africa (PRIDA), the Programme for Infrastructure Development in Africa (PIDA), the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), the African Union Financial Institutions (AUFIs), the Single African Air Transport Market (SAATM), the Free Movement of Persons (FMP), and the Malabo Convention, to support the development of a Digital Single Market (DSM), as part of the integration priorities of the African Union. Data governance is recognised as an essential cross-cutting theme to support the digital ecosystem” (Article 3²⁴).

Continued support for data protection authorities in Africa²⁰

52. Acknowledging that most African DPAs are in a nascent stage, further work to develop the institutional capacities of specific DPAs may assist with advancing the implementation of the Malabo Convention once it enters into force, while aligning and supporting the efforts of the RAPDP.

Awareness-raising activities²⁰

54. Previous assessments of obstacles to ratification within AU member states have noted that, except where member states have declared a specific reason for a delay in ratification, the likely factors include a lack of participation in negotiations, limited awareness of the convention or treaty, and inadequate mechanisms at national and regional levels to ensure ratification⁵⁶. In the light of this, the Roadmap proposes stakeholder engagements that address limited awareness of the Malabo Convention and promote active discussion on the issue of a lack of participation or ownership in the development of the Convention.

⁵⁵ Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020-2030), <https://au.int/en/documents/20200518/digital-transformation-strategy-africa-2020-2030>.

⁵⁶ Anywar, 'Consultant's Report of the Study on the Development of Strategy to Guide the Promotion of the Ratification of the Revised African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (i.e. the MAPUTO CONVENTION)' African Union Commission, 2016, <https://au.int/en/documents/20110718/consultants-report-study-development-strategy-guide-promotion-ratification>.

7 PROCEDURES TO ENSURE ETHICAL COMPLIANCE

A. HUMANS – INFORMED CONSENT

Due to the focus, approach, methodology and objectives of the project, research and innovation activities are not expected to raise any significant ethics related issues. Indeed, research activities will be very much limited to the identification and engagement of relevant actors and activities in the EU/Africa community with focus on: aquaculturists and agroecologists, with whom project activities will be implemented. The identification of these actors will be performed by each individual partner by screening their already available databases.

There is no participation of human subjects in the PrAEctiCe project activities. An informed consent form explaining in intelligible manner the purpose of the project have been prepared by the partners collecting data for farms mapping. The consent form explains how the data will be gathered, processed and stored for the beneficiaries.

B. THIRD COUNTRIES

The ethics, values and consequences of non-compliance of the 3 concerned countries – Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda have been described along with the specific regulations in Chapters 3, 4, 5 and 6 of this document.

C. BREACHES

In the unlikely event that a potential ethical issue is identified, the coordinator will organise a meeting with the beneficiary to analyse the situation and define with the partner a remediation action plan. If the remediation action plan is not implemented by the beneficiary, the coordinator will call for a general assembly to vote on the beneficiary exclusion. Breaches regarding the 'Conflict of Interest' were mentioned in Section 2.6 of this document. The information on breaches and conflicts regarding data protection in the AU have been mentioned in the relevant regulations stated in Chapters 3, 4, 5 and 6 of this document.

8 CONCLUSION

This deliverable confirms that all partners involved in PrAEctiCe are aware of the relevant regulatory frameworks and are adequately addressing ethical issues within the scope of the project. It provides an overview of the ethical issues that may arise as a result of the PrAEctiCe approach. It formally presents all relevant regulatory frameworks reviewed by the consortium and finally describes the actions taken to address the ethical requirements described in PrAEctiCe's Review of Ethical Principles and Relevant Legislation. The results of this deliverable are the ethical guidelines for the implementation of the PrAEctiCe project.

ANNEX I

Status List of the Malabo Convention as of May 2023.

AFRICAN UNION
الاتحاد الأفريقي

UNION AFRICAINE
UNIÃO AFRICANA

Addis Ababa, ETHIOPIA P.O. Box 3243 Telephone 517 700 AU, ADDIS ABABA

LIST OF COUNTRIES WHICH HAVE SIGNED, RATIFIED/ACCEDED TO THE
AFRICAN UNION CONVENTION ON CYBER SECURITY AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION

LISTE DES PAYS QUI ONT SIGNE, RATIFIE/ADHERE

CONVENTION DE L'UNION AFRICAINE SUR LA CYBERSECURITE ET LA PROTECTION DES DONNEES PERSONNELLES

12/05/2023

No	COUNTRY/PAYS	DATE OF/DE SIGNATURE	DATE OF/DE RATIFICATION/ ACCESSION	DATE DEPOSITED/ DATE DE DEPOT
1	Algeria	-	-	-
2	Angola	-	21/02/2020	11/05/2020
3	Benin	28/01/2015	-	-
4	Botswana	-	-	-
5	Burkina Faso	-	-	-
6	Burundi	-	-	-
7	Cameroon	12/08/2021	-	-
8	Central African Rep.	-	-	-
9	Cape Verde	-	13/11/2020	05/02/2022
10	Chad	14/06/2015	-	-
11	Côte d'Ivoire	-	08/03/2023	03/04/2023
12	Comoros	29/01/2018	-	-
13	Congo	12/06/2015	24/09/2020	23/10/2020
14	Djibouti	12/05/2023	-	-
15	Democratic Rep. of Congo	-	-	-
16	Egypt	-	-	-
17	Equatorial Guinea	-	-	-
18	Eritrea	-	-	-
19	Ethiopia	-	-	-
20	Gabon	-	-	-
21	Gambia	02/12/2022	-	-
22	Ghana	04/07/2017	13/05/2019	03/06/2019
23	Guinea-Bissau	31/01/2015	-	-
24	Guinea	-	31/07/2018	16/10/2018
25	Kenya	-	-	-
26	Libya	-	-	-
27	Lesotho	-	-	-
28	Liberia	-	-	-
29	Madagascar	-	-	-
30	Mali	-	-	-
31	Malawi	-	-	-
32	Morocco	-	-	-
33	Mozambique	29/06/2018	02/12/2019	21/01/2020
34	Mauritania	26/02/2015	19/04/2023	09/05/2023
35	Mauritius	-	06/03/2018	14/03/2018
36	Namibia	-	25/01/2019	01/02/2019
37	Nigeria	-	-	-
38	Niger	-	22/02/2022	16/03/2022
39	Rwanda	16/04/2019	14/11/2019	21/11/2019
40	South Africa	16/02/2023	-	-
41	Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic	-	-	-
42	Senegal	-	03/08/2016	16/08/2016
43	Seychelles	-	-	-
44	Sierra Leone	29/01/2016	-	-
45	Somalia	-	-	-
46	South Sudan	-	-	-
47	Sao Tome & Principe	29/01/2016	-	-
48	Sudan	15/03/2023	-	-

No	COUNTRY/PAYS	DATE OF/DE SIGNATURE	DATE OF/DE RATIFICATION/ ACCESSION	DATE DEPOSITED/ DATE DE DEPOT
49	Eswatini	-	-	-
50	Tanzania	-	-	-
51	Togo	02/04/2019	30/09/2021	19/10/2021
52	Tunisia	23/04/2019	-	-
53	Uganda	-	-	-
54	Zambia	29/01/2016	15/12/2020	24/03/2021
55	Zimbabwe	-	-	-
	Total countries : 55	of signature : 19	of ratification : 15	of deposit : 15

Note

- Adopted by the Twentythird Ordinary Session of the Assembly, held in Malabo, Equatorial Guinea, 27th June 2014.

The 3 countries concerned in this PrAectiCe project for the living labs – 25. Kenya, 50. Tanzania and 53. Uganda have not yet signed the Convention.